

SafeHabitus

Deliverable 4.3

**Youth perspectives of the
future attractiveness of
farming**

Deliverable description

Deliverable	Deliverable 4.3: Youth perspectives of the future attractiveness of farming
Due Date	31/12/2025
Actual submission date	16/12/2025
Project start date	01/01/2023
Duration	48 months
Work Package concerned	WP4
Concerned work package leader	Černič Istenič Majda
Dissemination level	[x] PU : Public (must be available on the website)
Authors	Béjar Fuentes, Mario (CEJA) Černič Istenič, Majda (ZRC SAZU) Knežević Hočevar, Duška (ZRC SAZU) Slovenč Grasselli, Mateja (ZRC SAZU) Tisa Kučan Lah (ZRC SAZU)
Revision history	08/10/2025 Draft version 07/11/2025 1 st review 26/11/2025 2 nd version 09/12/2025 3 rd version 14/12/2025 Final version
Statement of originality	This report presents the results of original research undertaken by the authors listed.

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the European Union**

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Executive Summary

Aim and purpose. This report examines how young and aspiring farmers across Europe perceive the conditions shaping agricultural work and how these conditions influence entry, retention, working life, succession, and well-being. By centring youth perspectives, it provides qualitative evidence the SafeHabitus research exploring issues associated with quality of life and well-being, and how these influence the attractiveness of farming. This research aims to enhance understanding of the working conditions of young and potential future farmers and provide evidence to inform policy development at EU and national level so that farming can be experienced as safer, fairer, and more attractive for the next generation.

Method. Five online focus groups were organised in cooperation with European Council of Young Farmers (CEJA) (January–February 2025), bringing together 17 participants (eight women, nine men) from 10 European countries. Each session (approximately 90 minutes) used a common scenario and open questions developed from Deliverable 4.1 and Deliverable 4.2 to explore four domains: (I) changing agricultural context, (II) generational change, (III) working conditions, and (IV) policy needs. Discussions were recorded with consent, transcribed, and thematically analysed.

Main findings. Research participants place their everyday experiences within a broader context of economic uncertainty, structural inequalities, and climate risk.

- In Theme I, they highlight price volatility, high input costs, weak bargaining power, administrative burden, and policy instability, along with pressure from “cheap/low-standard imports”. Diversification, short supply chains, and closer ties with consumers and communities are seen as key strategies for stability.
- In Theme II, access to land, capital, and affordable credit emerges as a major barrier to entry and succession, with family assets and informal transfer routes often decisive. Succession is described as a long, emotionally charged process requiring negotiation and mutual respect; women report additional obstacles linked to maternity, unpaid work, and recognition.
- Theme III illustrates how long working hours, blurred boundaries between work and private life, unavailability of or scarce replacement labour, and limited mental health support affect well-being and future plans. Technology can reduce physical strain but is limited by cost, skills gaps, and poor rural infrastructure, and sometimes creates new administrative burdens.
- In Theme IV, participants call for fairer markets, parity in social protection (including maternity/paternity leave, sickness cover, pensions, and mental health support), recognition of unpaid family work, better advisory and training systems, territorially sensitive policies for remote and protected areas, and public recognition of “quality European food”. Collectively, their perspectives outline the contours of a new social contract for farming that links dignity, autonomy, and well-being with economic viability and environmental responsibility.

Key message 1 – Young farmers want the same social rights as other young workers

Young and aspiring farmers do not seek special treatment; they want to be treated like other young people in any profession. They expect equal access to social security (health, pensions, sickness, accidents, unemployment), maternity and paternity protection, and mental health support. Currently, many face gaps, complex rules, or weaker protection simply because they are farmers or self-employed.

Implication: European and national policies must ensure **parity of social rights for young farmers and farm workers with other young workers**, so that choosing farming does not mean accepting inferior social protection.

Key message 2 – A fair and predictable operating environment is essential for generational renewal

Young farmers are ready to invest, innovate and take responsibility, but not when confronted with chronic price volatility, rising input costs, cheap imports and unstable policies. They have weak bargaining power and a heavy administrative burden, and view diversification and closer links to consumers as survival strategies rather than free choices.

Implication: CAP and national policies must **stabilise incomes and reduce uncertainty** (fair contracts, enforcement of Unfair Trading Practices, long-term schemes) if they want a new generation of farmers on the land.

Key message 3 – Quality of work and mental well-being are central to the future of European farming

Research participants report long and unpredictable working hours, blurred boundaries between work and private life, scarce replacement labour, and very limited access to mental health support. Although technology can ease some physical burdens, high costs, skills gaps, poor infrastructure, and increased administrative work create new sources of stress.

Implication: Making farming attractive and sustainable requires **placing working conditions, occupational safety and health, and mental well-being at the centre of agricultural, rural, and social policy**. This includes support for replacement labour, counselling, and advisory systems that address well-being, not just production.

Key message 4 – Young women in farming need visibility, rights and time, not just “empowerment” rhetoric

Young women in farming often bear a triple burden of farm work, off-farm employment and care responsibilities, much of which is invisible and unpaid. They face additional barriers in succession, decision-making and access to social security, particularly maternity protection

and pensions. These conditions make it risky to combine farming with family life, even when motivation is high.

Implication: A gender-just farming future requires **recognition of women's work, independent social rights and tailored support** – such as maternity cover, replacement services, childcare and leadership opportunities – designed and evaluated in collaboration with young women farmers.

The following table summarises the pathway from research findings to recommended actions, identifying responsible actors and indicative timeframes. Detailed recommendations are provided in the "Actions Needed" section. The relationships between themes, messages, and reforms are cross-cutting rather than one-to-one, reflecting the interconnected nature of the challenges.

Key Message	Core Finding	Priority Reform Area	Lead Actors	Timeframe
KM1: Social rights parity	Young farmers face gaps in health insurance, pensions, maternity/paternity cover, and mental health support compared to other professions	Reform 3: Achieve parity in social protection and care infrastructure	National governments; Social affairs ministries; CAP Managing Authorities	Medium-term (2–5 years)
KM2: Fair and predictable environment	Price volatility, weak bargaining power, cheap imports, and policy instability undermine investment and retention	Reform 1: Rebalance markets in favour of farm-level income security	EU (DG AGRI, DG COMP); National competition authorities; Producer organisations	Immediate to medium-term
KM3: Quality of work and well-being	Long hours, blurred work-life boundaries, scarce replacement labour, and limited mental health support affect retention	Reform 4: Simplify CAP instruments as enabling systems	EU (DG AGRI); CAP Managing Authorities; Paying agencies	Immediate to medium-term
	Remote and protected areas face higher costs,	Reform 5: Embed territorial	National/regional governments; Rural	Medium to long-term

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	weaker services, and greater obligations without adequate compensation	justice and safety/health outcomes	development authorities	
KM4: Young women's visibility and rights	Women bear triple burdens (farm, off-farm, care work), face barriers in succession and decision-making, and lack adequate maternity protection	Reform 3: Achieve parity in social protection (<i>with gender-specific design</i>)	National governments; Farmer organisations; Advisory services	Medium-term (2-5 years)

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Acknowledgements

First and foremost, we extend our warmest thanks to all the young farmers across Europe who took valuable time from their busy schedules to participate in our focus groups and candidly share their experiences, perceptions, visions, and insights into their lives, work, and future.

We express our sincere gratitude to the team at CEJA for their support for this work and, particularly, their assistance in establishing contact with the research participants and for distributing the invitations and focus group guidelines. We would also like to thank all the administrators of the SafeHabitus Communities of Practice who supported us in identifying additional research participants.

We express our thanks to our SafeHabitus Project Partners: Dr Laura Girdžiūtė, and Dr Sally Shortall for reviewing the focus group guidelines, and to Leo Guilfoyle and Dolores Hannick for the support.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context

As part of SafeHabitus, which aims to improve health and safety in agriculture, this report examines how to retain young people in farming. Policymakers refer to this as the “young farmer problem.” Since the 1980s, the EU’s Common Agricultural Policy has sought to attract youth with start-up support (European Commission, 2012; European Parliament, 2025). Young farmers are expected to sustain production and rural vitality and are often regarded as more open to modernisation, greener practices, and new business models.

A decade ago, Eurostat reported a persistent decline in the number of farms and farmers, alongside an unfavourable age structure. The Commission warned of a “worrying shortage of new farmers,” noting that only 6% of EU farmers were under 35, while over 55% were older than 55 (DGIP, 2012). Despite reinforced support, 2020 data still show an average farmer age of 57; only 6.5% were under 35 and just 4.2% were women (Eurostat, 2022). Policy documents continue to promise a more attractive, diverse agri-food sector (European Commission, 2024; European Parliament, 2023).

Research finds that CAP measures have had limited impact (Beck et al., 2024; EU CAP Network’s Thematic Group on Gen Z, 2024). Some argue that the picture is skewed by Eurostat’s focus on formal farm holders, overlooking other labour and decision-makers, especially successors and women (Bertolozzi-Caredio, 2024; Fischer & Burton, 2014; Sutherland, 2023; Zagata & Sutherland, 2015). The concern is global but especially pronounced in Europe. From 2000 to 2020, publications on generational renewal increased, with a first surge in 2007 linked to concerns about European agriculture (Bădan & Nicoleta, 2020). A systematic review (1990–2022) finds declining youth participation and few new entrants, driven by economic and structural obstacles (land access, low incomes, administrative burdens, weak bargaining power), socio-cultural factors (urban migration, weakened intergenerational knowledge transfer, stigma of “dirty, hard” work), and environmental risks (weather uncertainty) (Borda et al., 2023). It is this latter set of factors that are of key interest to the SafeHabitus project, i.e. perceptions of current and future working conditions and job quality.

1.2 Research objectives

The SafeHabitus project aims to improve the working conditions of farmers and farm workers in Europe, their health and safety at work, and their well-being. In assessing the future attractiveness of farming in particular (**WP4, Task 4.2**), the project aims to find out what young farmers and new entrants expect from agriculture as an occupation, what their working conditions should be like, and how these could be realised. To this end, virtual focus groups were undertaken with young and potential future farmers, both men and women, from across Europe to identify the impact of their perceptions on visions and plans for the future, including farm inheritance/takeover.

Based on the objectives of the SafeHabitus project and in particular **the objectives of WP4 (Task 4.2)**, a research question was defined to reflect the interactive, future-oriented and youth-centred nature of the investigation.

1.3 Main research question

The main research question reads:

How do young farmers across Europe perceive current and future trends affecting work in agriculture and how do these perceptions influence their decisions to enter or remain in agriculture, particularly in relation to working conditions, generational renewal, and the sustainability of rural employment?

1.4 Supporting questions

To further structure the investigation, the main research question is supported by the following additional questions:

1. *What are the main drivers of change that will influence employment conditions in agriculture in the coming decades (e.g. climate change, technological advances, policy changes)?*
2. *How do these factors influence the attractiveness of farming as a career and the likelihood of generational change in rural areas?*
3. *What expectations and challenges do young farmers see in terms of health, safety, and well-being in agricultural work?*
4. *What policy initiatives do young farmers believe are needed to support sustainable, safe, and rewarding careers in farming?*

1.5 Alignment with objectives and expected outcomes in Grant Agreement

This section relates the findings from the five focus groups to the three WP4 objectives (4.1–4.3) and two expected outcomes (EO1 and EO4). Table 1 summarises these alignments, marking ✓ where the evidence clearly and substantively addresses the objective/outcome, and ♦ where contributions are partial or directional (needs and pathways specified but implementation evidence lacking); a blank indicates weak or absent alignment.

1.5.1 Expected Outcome 1 — Enhanced understanding and awareness

EO1 seeks enhanced understanding and awareness by policy makers, farmers' organisations, trade unions and health authorities of farmers' and farm workers' health and

safety, and of the implications of their perceptions of their work on the future of the sector and long-term food security.

The eight integrated findings substantially advance EO1. They illuminate how structural, economic, social, environmental, cultural and territorial factors together shape the health, safety and well-being of farmers and farm workers, as well as the attractiveness of farming as a profession. Crucially, the results link conditions and perceptions in farming to the future of the sector and, by extension, to long-term food security.

1.5.2 Expected Outcome 4 — Improved health, safety and labour conditions through better frameworks and initiatives

EO4 seeks improved health, safety and labour conditions in farming through better performing European and national policy and legal frameworks and innovative bottom-up initiatives.

The findings offer strong insights and clear directions for change, identifying what needs to change in European and national policy and legal frameworks as well as in bottom-up practice — particularly in areas of social protection, accessible mental health support, payments for ecosystem services, climate adaptation measures, fairer market rules, improved access to land and finance, and "rural-proofed" investments in services and connectivity. However, the evidence remains at the level of identified needs, principles and proposed instruments. It does not yet describe concrete implemented schemes or initiatives with measurable improvements in working conditions, Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) outcomes or subjective well-being.

1.5.3 Alignment with WP4, Task 4.2

This deliverable directly fulfils the third step of Task 4.2, which specified that virtual focus groups organised with input from CEJA would engage young and potential future farmers from across the EU to draw out the implications of their perceptions for visions and plans for the future, including farm inheritance and takeover. The five focus groups conducted for this research (see Section 2 for full methodological details) addressed all four thematic areas specified in the task description and generated rich qualitative evidence directly relevant to the task's focus on attractiveness, working conditions, and long-term food security.

The discussions were structured around visions and scenarios developed in D4.2 and explored participants' perceptions of how current and future trends in agriculture shape their decisions to enter or remain in the sector. All four thematic areas — the changing agricultural context, generational change, working conditions, and policy needs — directly address the task's focus on the attractiveness of farming, labour and working conditions, and long-term food security. While the sample size (17) fell short of the indicative target of 30 young people and women specified in the Grant Agreement, the focus groups achieved strong gender balance and broad geographical coverage, and generated rich qualitative

evidence on the factors shaping young farmers' career trajectories and succession intentions.

Table 1 Matrix linking integrated findings to project objectives and expected outcomes

Finding	How it links	EO1	EO4	Evidence / examples
Labour, work-life balance, and social protection	Documents how workload, labour shortages, invisible family labour, and social protection gaps affect OSH, well-being, and retention in farming.	✓	✦	Accounts of overwork, blurred boundaries, gendered care burdens, lack of parity in maternity, pension, and healthcare; interest in mental health support.
Tension between tradition and innovation	Explains how intergenerational relations, authority, and identity shape the adoption of ecological, technological, and organisational change.	✓	✦	Younger farmers' limited decision-making space; friction over new practices; references to advisory and training needs and digital infrastructure gaps.
Territorial cohesion and rural infrastructure	Reveals how spatial inequalities in services, markets, and digital connectivity affect OSH, resilience, and the long-term prospects of farming.	✓	✦	Gaps in transport, healthcare, childcare, and broadband; higher costs and risks in remote areas; calls for 'rural-proofed' investments.
Economic uncertainty and market instability	Links price volatility, market concentration, and subsidy dependence to stress, planning horizons, and the attractiveness of farming.	✓	✦	Reports of volatile prices, unfair competition, and thin margins; calls for cost-reflective pricing and stricter regulation of the value chain.
Environmental stewardship vs. economic viability	Shows that environmental commitments are central to identity but can threaten viability without adequate incentives, such as payments for ecosystem services (PES).	✓	✦	Concerns about regulatory burden and climate risk; proposals for PES and locally adapted regulations.
Cultural recognition and public perception	Highlights how cultural marginalisation and misrecognition affect dignity, identity, and the attractiveness of farming.	✓		Experiences of stigma and misunderstanding; suggestions for food literacy and public campaigns that highlight the social value of farming.

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Structural inequalities and barriers to entry	Demonstrates how unequal access to land, capital, and succession pathways shapes generational renewal, viability, and perceptions of fairness.	✓	✦	High entry costs; policies favouring incumbents or family successors; new entrants with innovative ideas face structural obstacles.
Vision of the future: a new social contract for farming	Integrates economic, social, environmental, and cultural dimensions into a long-term vision for an attractive sector oriented towards 2060.	✓	✦	Future aspirations include combining fair markets, embedded social protection, climate adaptation, investment in human capital, and recognition.

Legend: ✓ = clearly/fully addressed; ✦ = partially or directionally addressed (needs implementation/impact evidence); blank = not substantively addressed.

2. Methods

2.1 Research design

This study employed a qualitative, exploratory research design using focus group methodology. Focus groups were chosen as the primary data collection method because they enable participants to interact with one another, build on each other's contributions, and surface shared experiences, tensions, and aspirations that might not emerge in individual interviews. This approach is particularly suited to understanding how young farmers collectively make sense of their circumstances and articulate their visions for the future. As specified in the Grant Agreement, virtual focus groups organised in cooperation with CEJA were designed to engage young and potential future farmers from across Europe to draw out the implications of their perceptions for visions and plans for the future, including farm inheritance and takeover.

2.2 Building on evidence from WP4 previous results (D4.1 and D4.2)

The design of the focus groups and the formulation of the guiding questions (see APPENDIX 1) draw directly on the evidence and conceptual frameworks developed in Deliverables 4.1 and 4.2. D4.1 provided a systematic overview of current and emerging stressors and drivers of change affecting farmers' working and living conditions, while D4.2 developed future-oriented scenarios with Communities of Practice (CoPs), highlighting how these drivers may evolve and interact over time. Together, these outputs informed both the selection of the four core topics (I–IV) and the precise wording of the questions addressed to young and aspiring farmers.

2.2.1 From systematic review (D4.1) to thematic focus

D4.1, *Current and future drivers of agricultural change: Assessing the implications for working conditions and occupational stress amongst farmers and farmworkers*, identified a wide range of sources of stress and vulnerability in agriculture, as well as structural and policy gaps that undermine health, safety and well-being. The report mapped:

- psychosocial and economic stressors (price volatility, debt, market dependence, uncertainty),
- environmental and climate-related pressures,
- occupational hazards and OSH risks,
- cultural norms and identities that shape risk-taking and help-seeking,
- gaps and inequalities in social protection systems, and
- the role of technological change as both a source of opportunity and new pressures.

Particular attention was paid to vulnerable groups – including women, migrant and seasonal workers, and young farmers – whose exposure to overlapping stressors is intensified by

labour market insecurity, limited bargaining power, and uneven access to support. D4.1 also emphasised that these challenges are embedded in broader macro-processes, such as neoliberal reform, globalisation, labour shortages, increased reliance on migrant labour, and climate change.

These insights guided the decision to centre the focus groups on four interrelated topics: the changing socio-economic and environmental context (Topic I), generational change and farm succession (Topic II), everyday working conditions and OSH (Topic III), and policy needs and institutional support (Topic IV). The questions under each topic translate D4.1's literature-based findings into an empirical exploration of how young and aspiring farmers themselves experience and interpret these pressures (See Appendix 1).

2.2.2 From foresight scenarios (D4.2) to focus group questions

D4.2, *Visions of the future of farming: Implications for working conditions and occupational stress*, extended the analysis by engaging CoP members in a foresight process that combined expert knowledge, stakeholder perspectives, and participatory scenario development. This work identified key drivers of change and explored their possible combinations in future farming scenarios, with particular attention to working conditions, OSH, and the attractiveness of farming as a livelihood.

The foresight exercises underscored several cross-cutting themes reflected in the focus group guide: increasing uncertainty and volatility in markets and policy frameworks; climate and environmental pressures; demographic ageing and difficulties of generational renewal; tensions around digitalisation and automation; and persistent gaps in social protection and recognition of farmers' work. D4.2 thus provided a forward-looking framework that helped to sharpen the focus group questions towards futures, aspirations, and perceived pathways of change, rather than only current problems.

Drawing on D4.1 and 4.2, four primary topics that would be explored in the focus groups were identified:

- **Topic I – Changing context** brings together D4.1's analysis of macro-level drivers (market volatility, climate change, technological and regulatory change) with D4.2's scenarios of possible futures. The questions invite participants to describe how they see the broader context evolving, how this affects their sense of security and control, and what it means for the future of their farms and communities.
- **Topic II – Generational change** builds on D4.1's identification of young farmers as a particularly vulnerable group and on D4.2's attention to demographic trends and succession challenges. The questions address access to land and capital, family expectations, intergenerational relationships, and the conditions under which young people would choose to enter, remain in, or exit farming.
- **Topic III – Working conditions** directly reflects D4.1's detailed mapping of psychosocial, physical and organisational stressors, as well as the discussion of vulnerable groups and OSH risks. It is also informed by D4.2's emphasis on how

different future pathways might intensify or alleviate work-related pressures. The questions address working time, mental and physical strain, safety practices, division of labour in households and on farms, and perceived changes over time.

- **Topic IV – Policy needs draws** on D4.1's identification of structural and policy gaps and on D4.2's foresight-based discussion of how policy choices could shape future working conditions and sector attractiveness. The questions ask participants to reflect on existing policies (e.g. CAP instruments, social protection, OSH regulations), to identify what works or fails in their contexts, and to suggest changes they consider necessary to make farming safer, fairer and more attractive for the next generation.

In sum, the focus group design in D4.3 is anchored in the cumulative knowledge produced in WP4. D4.1 provided a comprehensive, evidence-based mapping of current and emerging stressors and vulnerabilities, while D4.2 considered these within forward-looking scenarios that highlight possible futures for farming.

2.3 Ethics and consent

The focus group research was conducted in accordance with the ethical framework established for the SafeHabitus project and in full compliance with the International Sociological Association's Code of Ethics. All participants received written information about the research objectives, data handling procedures, and their rights prior to participation. Informed consent was obtained either through signed consent forms or recorded verbal consent at the start of each session. Participation was voluntary, and participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without consequence.

The Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (ZRC SAZU) institutional Code of Ethics came into effect on 29 November 2024, after preparatory activities for this task had commenced. An ethics application was subsequently submitted, and the research approach was confirmed as compliant with institutional requirements.

All empirical material — including video files, audio recordings, and transcripts — is stored securely on a password-protected shared drive on the Sociomedical Institute ZRC SAZU's internal network, with access restricted to the research team. Participant identities are protected through the use of anonymised numeric identifiers (e.g. #1, #2). Transcripts are available on request for research and audit purposes.

2.4 Sampling and recruitment

Participants were recruited through a multi-channel strategy. The primary recruitment channel was CEJA's membership network, which includes both current CEJA members and former participants in the CEJA leadership programme. In addition, all 11 SafeHabitus Communities of Practice (CoP) administrators were engaged during a WP2 meeting on 10 December 2024 and asked to mobilise their networks to support recruitment. CoP administrators subsequently assisted with additional recruitment efforts in January and

February 2025. A public call was also published on the SafeHabitus project webpage and social media platforms (LinkedIn, Facebook) on 11 December 2024.

All recipients of recruitment invitations were young farmers who already run their own farms or intend to do so in the future. The recruitment strategy prioritised diversity in terms of gender, country of origin, farm type, and stage in farming career. However, it should be noted that no formal register of new entrants to farming exists at European level; consequently, the sample is weighted towards established young farmers rather than aspiring entrants, with only two participants from non-farming backgrounds.

The Grant Agreement specified a target of two focus groups with 30 young people and women. Despite sustained recruitment efforts, response rates were lower than anticipated, attributed to the time constraints facing working farmers, limited English proficiency among some potential participants, and the timing of recruitment during a period that, while relatively quieter agriculturally, still posed challenges for farmer availability. Ultimately, 28 potential participants were contacted; of these, 17 participated across five focus groups. A detailed account of recruitment challenges and responses is provided in the section "Methodological considerations and limitations."

2.5 Participants

Seventeen young farmers (eight women, nine men) from ten European countries participated in the research: Austria (2), Belgium (1), Estonia (1), France (2), Ireland (2), Italy (1), Poland (3), Portugal (1), Slovenia (3), and the United Kingdom (1). Participants represented diverse farm types, including dairy, beef, pig, cereal, organic vegetable, and mixed farming operations, ranging from small family holdings to farms of 300 hectares. Their roles varied from owner-operators and co-managers to successors working alongside parents or other family members. Two participants were new entrants from non-farming backgrounds. Full participant characteristics are provided in **APPENDIX 2**.

2.6 Data collection

Five online focus groups were conducted between January and February 2025 via Zoom videoconference. The decision to conduct focus groups online was made in agreement with the project coordinator, as in-person meetings were considered logistically demanding and costly given the need to cover participants' travel and accommodation, and practically difficult given that farmers rarely have the opportunity to leave their farms for several days.

Each session lasted approximately 90 minutes and was scheduled at times intended to accommodate farming routines (10:00–11:30 or 16:00–17:30 Central European Time). Groups comprised between two and five participants, with a moderator and co-moderator from the ZRC SAZU research team. The moderator guided the discussion, while the co-moderator took notes, monitored time, and managed technical issues. All discussions were conducted in English.

The focus groups followed a semi-structured moderator guide (**APPENDIX 3**) organised around four thematic areas derived from the evidence base established in D4.1 and D4.2:

- **Theme I — Changing agricultural context:** drivers of change, current position, implications for career decisions and mental health
- **Theme II — Generational renewal:** conditions for succession, qualities of successful young farmers, farm status, gender considerations, vision for the farm to pass on
- **Theme III — Working conditions:** factors shaping working environment, future challenges and opportunities, health and safety
- **Theme IV — Policy needs:** CAP and national policy priorities, social protection, specific measures for young farmers

The full list of topics and guiding questions is provided in **APPENDIX 1**.

Sessions were audio- and video-recorded with participants' consent. Recordings were transcribed verbatim by members of the research team. Transcripts were anonymised, with participants assigned numeric identifiers that are used consistently throughout this report.

2.7 Data analysis

Transcripts were analysed using thematic synthesis methodology (Krippendorff, 2004). The analysis proceeded through five stages:

1. **Data familiarisation:** Researchers thoroughly read all focus group transcripts multiple times, organising responses by both question and focus group.
2. **Thematic coding:** An inductive coding strategy was employed, allowing themes to emerge from the data rather than imposing predetermined categories. Coding captured both surface-level (semantic) content and deeper (latent) meanings.
3. **Cross-group synthesis:** Patterns were identified across different participant demographics and national contexts, noting areas of consensus and divergence.
4. **Theme hierarchisation and mapping:** Subthemes were aggregated under broader thematic categories (e.g. structural challenges, environmental change). Interrelations between themes were derived from the integrated coding, see Table 2, by identifying: (a) repeated co-occurrence of codes within the same meaning units; (b) recurrent co-presence of themes across scenario questions; and (c) related codes indicating that one theme systematically frames, qualifies, or intensifies another. The resulting thematic networks are visualised as conceptual graphs using a force-directed layout.

5. **Interpretive synthesis:** Findings were contextualised within wider socio-economic and political frameworks influencing young farmers. Quotations are used throughout this report to exemplify each subtheme, ensuring that interpretations remain grounded in participants lived experiences.

Thematic saturation was reached when further coding reinforced existing themes without generating new ones.

The research was planned and implemented by the ZRC SAZU research team led by Črnič Istenič. Slovenc Grasselli and Kučan Lah checked the transcription, while the analysis of the data was conducted by Črnič Istenič and Knežević Hočevar. Given the exploratory nature of the study and the emphasis on capturing diverse perspectives rather than achieving inter-coder reliability in a quantitative sense, formal inter-rater reliability testing was not conducted. However, emerging codes and themes were discussed among team members throughout the analytical process to enhance consistency and interpretive rigour.

2.8 Reflexivity

The research team acknowledges that the thematic analysis and observations are shaped by the analysts' disciplinary backgrounds in rural sociology and agricultural studies, which may introduce interpretive orientation. A reflexivity statement documenting the team's observations on the strengths and limitations of the online focus group format, including the breadth of topics covered, language barriers, and group dynamics, is provided in **APPENDIX 6**.

2.9 Methodological considerations and limitations

A detailed discussion of methodological limitations is provided in Section 4.3 (Methodological considerations and limitations) following the main findings.

3. Results

In this chapter, we present the cross-cutting findings from all Themes (I–IV), comparing them with existing research and policy documents on the attractiveness of farming as a career for young people, as well as other results in WP4, D4.1, and D4.2. The detailed results, including conceptual mapping and participant quotes, and the assessment of these are provided in **APPENDIX 5**.

The integrated results from Themes I–IV (Table 2; Appendix 7) show that European young farmers operate within a complex and interdependent set of challenges and opportunities, where structural, cultural, ecological, and political dimensions' overlap. These empirical findings are closely aligned with much of the academic and policy literature, which views many of the challenges faced by young farmers as deeply embedded in structural

inequalities, policy inadequacies and cultural dynamics, rather than as isolated, individual constraints. However, compared to the literature discussed below, our findings highlight a particular constellation of overarching themes that shape the lived realities and aspirations of the participants. Each of the themes described below is not novel in itself. What is new, however, is their constellation, through which the participants convey not only the current challenges and hopes that they experience and simultaneously imagine (i.e. the duality of their statements), but also their limited agency. In other words, if participants emphasise that the farm of tomorrow should not only be a modern, productive enterprise, but also a legacy that enables their potential successors to feel good (well-being) and live a dignified and good life, then the first recommendation to policy makers is the need addressed this constellation of issues in parallel or simultaneously in order to be effective.

Table 2: Integrated findings of all Themes (I-IV)

Thematic Area	Description
Structural Inequalities and Barriers to Entry	Young farmers face structural exclusion through unequal access to land, capital, and succession, with policies favouring established, male-led family farms and reinforcing generational inequality.
Economic Insecurity and Market Vulnerability	Unfair markets, volatile prices, and exposure to low-standard imports create chronic economic insecurity, making farmers heavily dependent on CAP subsidies and limiting investment and succession.
Labour, Work-Life Balance, and Social Protection	Labour shortages, heavy workloads, blurred work-life boundaries, and weak social protection, especially for women, reduce quality of life and undermine long-term commitment to farming.
Tension Between Tradition and Innovation	Young farmers value tradition but seek autonomy to innovate ecologically and technologically, often constrained by family hierarchies, poor digital infrastructure, and uneven access to training.
Environmental Stewardship vs. Economic Viability	Environmental commitments are central to farming identities, but current policies often make ecological measures financially risky without adequate payment for ecosystem services or context-sensitive regulation.
Cultural Recognition and Public Perception	Farming suffers from cultural marginalisation and low food literacy, weakening its status as a modern, skilled profession and making it harder to attract new entrants and gain public support.
Territorial Cohesion and Rural Infrastructure	Spatial disparities in services, markets, and digital access, especially in remote and mountain areas, raise costs, limit opportunities, and deepen structural inequalities for young farmers.
Vision of the Future: A New Social Contract for Farming	Young farmers envision agriculture that is fair, inclusive, sustainable, and respected, supported by enabling policies, social protection, and market conditions that secure dignity and autonomy.

3.1 Structural inequalities and barriers to entry

Across all Themes (I–IV), the most frequently cited obstacle is unequal access to land, capital, and viable succession pathways. Research participants report that this structural barrier extends beyond market dynamics; it is embedded in policy frameworks that favour established family farms and male-run businesses, systematically disadvantaging women and non-traditional (new) entrants. Rising land prices, credit systems tied to parental guarantees, and inadequately targeted CAP measures perpetuate this inequality.

This finding supports D4.1's identification of unequal access to land, capital, and stable markets as structural determinants shaping the entry conditions of European farmers. It extends this evidence by showing how these barriers specifically affect young people, women, and newcomers across different territorial contexts. It also deepens D4.2's account of future risks to farm viability. In particular, it highlights how structural inequalities directly constrain young farmers' capacity to pursue the dignified and autonomous farming futures envisioned in scenario-based analyses.

This finding also aligns with Sutherland's (2023) critique that the so-called "age crisis" in EU agriculture is less about attracting young people to the sector and more about overcoming the closed nature of farm ownership. Generational renewal policies – particularly under the CAP – tend to direct resources to family successors rather than genuinely opening the profession to new entrants. These new entrants often bring significant potential for innovation but lack capital and land. Coopmans et al. (2021) argue that generational renewal is best understood through a life course perspective that recognises multiple entry points into farming, not just succession from parents to children. This perspective views the barriers identified in Themes I–IV (land prices, capital, succession bottlenecks) as part of a broader path dependency. Institutional arrangements, inheritance laws, and CAP frameworks systematically channel resources to intra-family successors and marginalise new entrants. The study emphasises that these barriers are not only economic but also socially and institutionally embedded, reflecting the structural entrenchment described in the focus group data. All this confirms previous analyses (Fischer & Burton, 2014; Davis et al., 2013; Nordin & Lovén, 2020), which show that such structural exclusion is self-perpetuating without targeted measures.

The CAP Network (2024) background paper also emphasises that land availability, affordability, and competition from non-agricultural uses are the main structural barriers for new entrants. This is especially the case for those without a family farming background. The focus group's finding on unequal access to land, capital, and succession pathways is further strongly mirrored in CEJA's (2017) analysis. CEJA identifies access to land as the "primary obstacle" to farm installation and expansion. It also advocates for an EU-level land observatory (CEJA, 2025b), binding targets for no net land take by 2050, and targeted start-up programmes that prioritise small, sustainable, and environmentally committed farms. Importantly, CEJA also links structural inequality to intergenerational land mobility. Older farmers' reluctance to transfer farms exacerbates barriers to entry. This factor is closely related to the tensions in intergenerational negotiations described in Theme II.

The so-called generational crisis therefore does not appear to result from youth disinterest, but rather from structural marginalisation exacerbated by institutional inertia.

3.2 Economic uncertainty and market instability

Economic instability is a common thread, running through the discussions on working conditions (Theme III) and policy needs (Theme IV) as well as drivers of change (Theme I). Farmers identify market fairness, price predictability, and protection against cheap and low-standard imports (e.g. from MERCOSUR countries) as prerequisites for sustainability. They place these above subsidies in their hierarchy of needs. Over-reliance on CAP subsidies without addressing systemic market imbalances creates a fragile economic base. This exposes farmers to external shocks and undermines their ability to invest in innovation or succession.

This finding confirms D4.1's analysis that market volatility, unequal bargaining power, and structural exposure to risk are key stressors in European agriculture. It extends this evidence by showing that young farmers experience these forces as threats to long-term viability. It also reinforces D4.2's scenarios by demonstrating that unstable markets directly affect young people's willingness to enter or remain in farming under different future trajectories.

Potter & Lobley (1996a, 1996b) and Aldanondo-Ochoa et al. (2007) have also shown that unstable markets delay succession and drive potential entrants to work off-farm. The literature on succession cycles suggests that farms with identified successors tend to invest and expand. Farms without successors often downsize, exacerbating local economic fragility (Fischer & Burton, 2014; Calus et al., 2008).

Young farmers' concerns about price volatility, market concentration, and unfair trade competition also reflect the 2024 CAP Network's finding that market instability – exacerbated by global trade agreements – undermines the resilience of smaller producers. The emphasis on market fairness over subsidies in Themes I and IV also aligns with CEJA's (2024) call for forward-looking pricing models based on production costs and the explicit prohibition of below-cost selling. CEJA also prioritises tailored financial instruments for young farmers. CEJA notes that they are "two to three times more likely" to be rejected for loans than older farmers, mainly due to a perceived high-risk profile and lack of collateral. This deepens the cycles of vulnerability already observed in the empirical data.

The vulnerability of the market thus appears to be both a cause and a consequence of generational stagnation. This highlights the call in Theme IV to integrate market protection measures into generational renewal policy, rather than relying solely on financial support.

3.3 Labour, work-life balance, and social protection

Labour shortages (Theme I) overlap with mental health and invisible workloads (Theme III) and are exacerbated by the lack of adequate social protection measures (Theme IV). According to the participants, the high physical and emotional demands of farming are

intensified by the blurring of work–life boundaries. This is especially the case for women, who take on a disproportionate amount of domestic and caring responsibilities. The lack of maternity leave, parity healthcare, and mental health provision not only affects retention in the sector, but also impacts the quality of life in farming communities. Unsurprisingly, participants called for an agricultural system that offers farmers the same social protection as other occupational groups.

This finding supports D4.1’s identification of excessive workload, blurred work–life boundaries, invisible and gendered labour, and social protection gaps as central determinants of stress and OSH risks. It also provides detail on how young farmers internalise or resist these pressures. Additionally, it refines D4.2’s scenarios by showing that autonomy, mental health, access to replacement labour, and time flexibility are decisive factors for young farmers. These elements shape whether young people can envisage a sustainable, long-term future in farming.

The literature on farm succession, gender, and work–life balance on farms (e.g., Černič Istenič, 2024; Conway et al., 2019; Suess-Reyes & Fuetsch, 2016; Bock & Shortall, 2016) confirms that these are not marginal issues but central to the renewal of the sector. It emphasises the focus groups’ calls for parity in maternity, health, and pensions as integral to the attractiveness of farming. Recently, Nye et al. (2025) have even called for a coordinated international research agenda to address key gaps and priorities in mental health and well-being studies among farming communities in the Global North. They focus on who and what is being researched, geographical and methodological gaps, and existing or needed support systems.

Sutherland’s (2023) policy analysis highlights that current CAP structures cannot integrate gender equality obligations, despite formal EU treaty commitments. CEJA (2024) explicitly addresses these concerns, calling for an action plan for mental health in agriculture and rural areas, parity in social protection, and recognition of unpaid family labour in pension entitlements. Such measures should recognise well-being as an element of agricultural resilience rather than a peripheral welfare issue.

3.4 Tension between tradition and innovation

In the debate on generational renewal (Theme II) and the broader considerations of technological modernisation (Themes I and III), there is a persistent tension between preserving inherited farming traditions and embracing adaptive innovation. Although younger farmers value the knowledge and ethos of previous generations, they seek autonomy to introduce ecological, technological, and organisational reforms. These efforts are often hindered by entrenched decision-making hierarchies, insufficient digital infrastructure, and unequal access to training.

This finding supports D4.1’s identification of technological change, digital divides, and intergenerational authority as key drivers shaping the future of work in agriculture. It extends these insights by showing how young farmers negotiate autonomy and innovation

within inherited family systems. It also reinforces D4.2's argument that future-ready agriculture depends on adaptive learning and decision-making autonomy. Moreover, it shows how these capacities are shaped by real interpersonal constraints and unequal access to knowledge and technology.

Previous studies, e.g. by Gasson & Errington (1993) and Potter & Lobley (1996a), have emphasised that these negotiations often determine whether the farm evolves or remains stuck in the models of the past. This is consistent with the focus groups' accounts of limited decision-making freedom under older generations. The narratives of Theme II, which focus on the negotiation of modernisation within inherited systems, are closely related to Fischer & Burton's (2014) concept of succession as an "endogenous social process" in which identity, trust, and authority are negotiated alongside economic decisions. The life course model of Coopmans et al. (2021) adds that the adoption of innovations is highly dependent on the timing and nature of succession, as well as the quality of relationships between generations. On the other hand, Zagata & Sutherland (2015) find that successors often modernise within existing systems, while new entrants are more likely to initiate transformative change. Yet they remain structurally disadvantaged within the policy framework.

The CAP 2024 background paper highlights that younger farmers possess a higher level of formal agricultural education (21.4% compared to 3.6% for those over 65) and are early adopters of digital and ecological innovation. CEJA's policy vision (2024) addresses this gap by placing knowledge, education, and innovation at the core of generational renewal. CEJA advocates tailored advisory services covering environmental sustainability, business management, and new technologies, as well as the involvement of young farmers in Horizon Europe research consortia. This directly responds to the focus group's call for autonomy in shaping the future direction of the farm.

3.5 Environmental stewardship vs. economic viability

Environmental considerations are recognised as an integral part of farming identity, but current policy mechanisms often pit ecological compliance against financial sustainability. Farmers consistently argue for payment for ecosystem services, integration of conservation objectives with economic viability, and contextualised environmental regulation that reflects the realities of different geographical regions. Without these measures, environmental policies risk deepening inequalities and preventing generational renewal. The finding confirms D4.1's identification of climate change, ecological obligations, and regulatory complexity as major future drivers of workload, financial strain, and risk in farming. It also extends D4.2's analysis by showing how young farmers translate abstract ideas of a just ecological transition into concrete demands. These include payment for ecosystem services, contextualised regulation, and practical climate adaptation support.

Research on generational change also shows that while young farmers are willing to adopt sustainable practices, their ability to do so depends heavily on access to appropriate funding, training, and supportive institutional mechanisms (Sutherland, 2023; Zagata & Sutherland,

2015). Without this support, environmental obligations can reinforce structural inequalities by favouring incumbents and excluding new entrants.

The CEJA's 2017 position paper described young farmers as custodians of the countryside and argued that sustainability should be recognised as a public good under the CAP and rewarded accordingly. In its more recent work (2024 Toolkit), the CEJA emphasises the need to "support climate adaptation" to ensure that environmental protection and farm profitability are not mutually exclusive. The balance between environmental goals and farm viability is also addressed in the 2024 CAP background paper, which highlights that young farmers are at the forefront of climate change. At the same time, it warns that young farmers require a "climate transition toolkit" (especially funding, knowledge, and education) to make environmental stewardship viable. Together, these perspectives highlight the need to reconcile ecological measures with economic incentives if intergenerational renewal is to be equitable and sustainable.

3.6 Cultural recognition and public perception

The cultural marginalisation of agriculture is a subtle yet significant driver of other structural problems. Themes II and IV highlight the gap between society's perception and the reality of modern agriculture. Young farmers are calling for public education campaigns to increase food literacy and reposition farming as a skilled, essential, and modern profession. This cultural recognition is not only a matter of dignity but also a strategic necessity to attract new entrants and secure societal support for policy reform. By highlighting this point, the finding supports D4.1's observation that cultural devaluation and misperceptions of farming contribute to stress, stigma, and recruitment challenges. It also extends D4.2's future-oriented analysis by showing that young farmers consider public education, food literacy, and narrative change essential for creating an attractive and socially valued agricultural sector.

Sutherland (2023) describes this discrepancy as a social justice issue, noting that farming remains culturally coded as male, white, and traditional, with little recognition of diversity or innovation. CEJA (2021) identifies cultural recognition as a policy lever and advocates public education campaigns to improve food literacy and restore the image of agriculture as a skilled, modern, and important profession. This aligns with Coopmans et al. (2021), who find that societal recognition is part of the environment enabling generational renewal in farming.

3.7 Territorial cohesion and rural infrastructure

Geographical inequalities in access to markets, rural services, education, and digital infrastructure are evident in Themes I and IV. Young farmers in remote and mountainous areas face higher operating costs and limited access to opportunities, which exacerbates structural inequalities. Addressing rural infrastructure deficits is essential for economic stability and social cohesion. This finding supports D4.1's identification of territorial inequality, infrastructure deficits, and digital divides as structural drivers limiting rural

employment and farming viability. It also extends D4.2's emphasis on place-sensitive agricultural futures by showing that young farmers directly link rural services, mobility, digital access, and market proximity to their ability to enter, sustain, and modernise farming.

Academic studies confirm that regional inequalities in infrastructure, market access, and off-farm opportunities have a strong influence on whether farming is seen as a viable livelihood (Calus et al., 2008; Coopmans et al., 2021; Sutherland et al., 2014). A generational renewal policy based on uniform criteria runs the risk of ignoring these spatial inequalities, and structurally disadvantaging some rural regions (Zagata & Sutherland, 2015).

CEJA has repeatedly called for greater investment in rural infrastructure as a prerequisite for intergenerational regeneration. In 2017, it argued that young people in rural areas should have the same access to services as their urban peers, explicitly emphasising broadband and education as crucial prerequisites. More recently, in 2024, CEJA reaffirmed the principle of rural proofing in all EU policies and warned that rural infrastructure should not be funded solely from agricultural budgets. A coordinated cross-policy approach is required, linking the CAP with cohesion policy. Both academic and policy perspectives agree that territorial cohesion is fundamental to economic resilience and social justice in the generational renewal of farming.

3.8 Vision of the future: a new social contract for farming

Despite significant structural challenges, the narratives across all themes converge on a transformative vision: a farming sector that is economically viable, socially inclusive, environmentally sustainable, and culturally valued. Achieving this requires policy reforms that combine fair market conditions with embedded social protection, investment in human capital, and a shift from bureaucratic control to enabling frameworks. Farmers' hopes focus on a new agricultural paradigm in which dignity, autonomy, and mutual care define the profession as much as productivity.

This finding further highlights D4.1's identification of structural deficits in markets, land regimes, and social protection as drivers of perceived injustice within the sector. It also clarifies how young farmers translate these problems into concrete policy expectations. In addition, it operationalises D4.2's forward-looking visions by identifying the specific policy levers that young farmers consider essential for the sector's future. These include fair markets, inclusive land access, comprehensive social rights, practical environmental ambition, and territorially just rural infrastructures. Together, these elements are seen as crucial for securing the attractiveness and sustainability of farming careers.

The focus group's hopes align with Coopmans et al.'s (2021) warning that, without systemic integration of market, society, environment, and culture, generational renewal will remain fragmented and fragile. The wider literature (Fischer & Burton, 2014; Zagata & Sutherland, 2015; Sutherland, 2023) also confirms that succession is both a political and cultural turning point. It is the moment when entrenched hierarchies can either be strengthened or reconfigured in line with new paradigms of collaborative, adaptive, and socially valued

farming. The focus group's vision also reflects CEJA's proposed EU Action Plan (2024), which sees farmers as "stewards of land, culture, and community", with policies that guarantee dignity, autonomy, and sustainability.

4. Conclusions and implications

Based on the results outlined above and detailed in the Appendices 5 and 7, here are the conclusions in the form of answers to the four initial supporting research questions and then to the main research question:

1. *What are the main drivers of change that will influence employment conditions in agriculture in the coming decades (e.g. climate change, technological advances, policy changes)?*

Young European farmers believe that employment conditions in agriculture in the coming decades will be shaped by a complex interplay of climate change, technological advances and changing political conditions, all against a backdrop of deep-rooted economic uncertainty and structural barriers. Climate change, now an immediate reality, is altering crop calendars, pest pressures and compliance requirements, bringing with it both the need to adapt and the risk of destabilising production. Technological innovations – from precision farming to artificial intelligence – offer efficiency gains but also risk deepening inequalities through the persistent rural digital divide and unequal access to training. Policy volatility, trade liberalisation and bureaucratic burdens erode long-term planning, while high land prices, debt burdens and distorted value chains undermine profitability and prevent generational renewal. Labour shortages caused by low wages, unattractive working conditions and an ageing workforce further exacerbate the vulnerability of the sector.

But alongside this pressure, there are also adaptation strategies: Diversification into local markets, niche production and community-based models – often led by women farmers – point to a more autonomous, socially embedded agricultural future. For young farmers, these drivers are not just external forces to be endured, but arenas of agency, where collective action, inclusive leadership and equitable access to technology can transform structural vulnerability into resilient and sustainable employment.

2. *How do these factors influence the attractiveness of farming as a career and the likelihood of generational change in rural areas?*

The attractiveness of farming as a profession and the prospects for generational renewal in rural areas are shaped by a tension between inherited traditions and the desire for innovation, exacerbated by structural barriers such as inflated land prices, restrictive access to capital and gendered policies that disadvantage women and newcomers. Succession involves not only financial and legal arrangements, but also emotional labour that requires resilience to cope with intergenerational friction, identity shifts and psychological strain. Negative societal perceptions, climate volatility, market instability and political uncertainty further discourage engagement, especially for those inheriting undercapitalised farms. Unequal access to practical training widens the gap between well-resourced farms and smallholder farmers or those without farming background, reinforcing disparities.

However, young farmers' visions of economically viable, technologically modern and socially valued agriculture reflect a strong aspiration for change – an aspiration that depends on the willingness of policies and institutions to empower, rather than hinder, the next generation.

3. *What expectations and challenges do young farmers see in terms of health, safety and well-being in agricultural work?*

Young farmers perceive that health, safety and well-being in agriculture are shaped by a challenging interplay of structural, cultural and personal pressures, with the normalisation of overwork, gender inequality and economic vulnerability undermining both physical and mental resilience. The blurring of boundaries between work and home life – caused by constant seasonal and animal care cycles – combined with a lack of maternity provision, external replacement labour, and predictable rest periods, leads to chronic stress, particularly for women who disproportionately take on domestic and agricultural responsibilities. Mental health issues such as stress, isolation and anxiety are widespread but culturally silenced, while public hostility towards certain agricultural sectors and bureaucratic surveillance exacerbate the emotional toll. Labour shortages force reliance on unpaid family work, further entangling economic survival with family tensions. Technological modernisation is seen as a potential remedy for physical stress and labour shortages, but its benefits are unevenly distributed due to cost, training and infrastructure barriers.

Against this backdrop, young farmers envision a cultural and systemic shift towards fairer markets, reliable political support, cooperative labour schemes, and inclusive childcare – underpinned by the belief that care for the land must include care for the farmers themselves. In this vision, technological change serves human well-being as well as productivity by redefining agricultural work as dignified, autonomous and socially connected, making it a sustainable and respected profession.

4. *What policy initiatives do young farmers believe are needed to support sustainable, safe, and rewarding careers in farming?*

Young European farmers articulate a clear and urgent need for policy reforms that bring agricultural policy – in particular the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) – in line with the lived reality of farming and aim to create sustainable, safe, and rewarding careers. They call for measures that reduce structural barriers to entry through targeted support for new entrants, small producers and environmentally committed farms, as well as pension incentives for older farmers and non-family transfer mechanisms that ensure equitable access to land and capital.

Economic stability underpinned by fair markets, predictable prices and protection from cheap imports is seen as essential to reduce dependence on subsidies.

A simplified, transparent and renewal-orientated CAP is called for to replace bureaucratic complexity with incentives for investment, sustainable employment and fairly remunerated environmental protection.

Comprehensive social protection – including maternity leave, healthcare, pensions, mental health support and recognition of unpaid family work – is identified as crucial for inclusion and work-life balance.

Regionally tailored measures to address the structural disadvantages of marginalised areas, combined with investment in rural education, infrastructure and digital access, are seen as crucial to retaining young people in agriculture.

Finally, farmers are seeking cultural recognition through public education and the defence of European quality standards in trade negotiations. They envision a new social contract that values them not only as food producers, but also as custodians of land, culture and community, ensuring dignity, autonomy and long-term resilience.

Main research question: *How do young farmers across Europe perceive current and future trends affecting work in agriculture and how do these perceptions influence their decisions to enter or remain in agriculture, particularly in relation to working conditions, generational renewal and the sustainability of rural employment?*

Young farmers across Europe perceive current and future trends in agriculture through a lens shaped by intertwined economic, environmental, technological and social forces that together influence both their willingness to enter the profession and their ability to stay in it.

Climate change, technological advances and policy volatility are seen as key drivers that are changing production conditions, reshaping labour needs and challenging long-term planning, while structural barriers – high land prices, unequal access to capital and gender exclusion – are limiting opportunities for generational renewal.

The attractiveness of agriculture is also limited by chronic economic insecurity, labour shortages and societal misperceptions.

Added to this are demanding working conditions characterised by blurred boundaries between work and private life, psychological stress and the normalisation of overwork.

Although technological modernisation offers prospects for easing physical strain and improving efficiency, its benefits remain unequally distributed without equitable access to skills, infrastructure and investment.

In response, young farmers are formulating a vision for an agricultural future that is economically viable, socially inclusive and environmentally sustainable. This vision is underpinned by policy reforms that remove barriers to entry, ensure fair markets, include comprehensive social protection and recognise farming as both a profession and a public good. Their aspirations reveal a desire to transform structural vulnerability into resilience through diversification, cooperative labour models, community-based markets and equitable technology use – conditions they see as essential to sustaining rural employment and ensuring a dignified, autonomous future for the next generation of farmers.

4.1 Implications for policy and practice

The key messages from the focus group results are presented in the previous chapters and highlighted in the summary at the beginning of this report. They emphasise what young farmers consider essential conditions for an attractive, safe, and sustainable future for agriculture. This subsection, however, translates these messages into system-level guidelines for policymakers at EU and national levels. Rather than restating the findings, it sets out how existing instruments – particularly the CAP, social protection systems, and rural development policies – should be redesigned. The aim is to systematically reduce entry barriers, stabilise incomes, and improve working conditions and well-being for the next generation of farmers.

The analysis shows that making agricultural professions more attractive, secure, and sustainable for young people – including women and new entrants – requires a change in policy design. Rather than addressing market failures after they occur, policymakers should establish incentive institutions in advance. At the European level, this involves embedding fair trading conditions, generational renewal, and social protection into the core structure of the CAP and related policies. At the Member State level, it means turning these priorities into practical measures that reduce entry barriers, stabilise incomes, and lower workloads and risks in specific territorial contexts. The main goal is to ensure that farmers have the same social rights, economic stability, and job opportunities as other professional groups.

A key implication concerns market governance. Evidence of income volatility and weak bargaining power at the farm level indicates that price support through coupled or decoupled payments is insufficient. Such support must be accompanied by rules to prevent value extraction downstream. Policies must therefore prioritise strengthened enforcement of the Unfair Trading Practices (UTP) framework, the development of reference tools for establishing production costs in contracts, support for producer organisations, and the strategic use of public procurement as core instruments for generational renewal. These should not be treated as optional add-ons to income support or competition policy. Place-based quality recognition can create stable demand for local, diversified production, which participants associate with improved prospects for young and women-led farms. Trade policy coherence is also necessary. This includes defending EU food quality and production standard benchmarks in trade agreements and ensuring timely protection against destabilising import surges, to reduce the offloading of compliance costs onto EU farms.

A second implication concerns intergenerational renewal, land access, and succession. The analysis highlights that entry into farming still depends disproportionately on family collateral and informal transfer pathways. At Member State level, targeted start-up finance that emphasises guarantees and early-years working capital can decouple initial installation from parental assets. Land-mobility instruments – such as land-matching services, tax incentives for early transfer, pre-emption, and lease facilitation – are likely to increase supply for non-family entrants and women. Succession should be viewed as a process rather than a single event: advisory ‘succession clinics’ that combine legal, financial, and psychosocial

support can mitigate conflict, establish co-decision mechanisms during overlapping generations, and improve the persistence of new installations over time. Member States should explicitly link these tools to measurable improvements in women's and non-family entrants' access to land and the survival rates of new installations, rather than focusing solely on the number of start-up projects supported.

Thirdly, the report's findings highlight a persistent imbalance between production incentives and social protection. To retain new entrants and reduce exits, achieving parity with non-farm professions is crucial: maternity and paternity leave for farm managers and contributing family workers; sickness cover with replacement services; and pension portability that recognises unpaid family labour. At the same time, mental health should be systematically integrated into advisory systems through confidential, farm-literate counselling and peer support. Replacement-labour vouchers and cooperative labour pools can help farmers take genuine time off, complete training, and manage seasonal peaks more safely. Generational renewal strategies should therefore be co-designed with social ministries so that maternity, sickness, pension, and mental health provisions for farmers reach parity with those for non-farm professions over the next programming period.

Administrative complexity has emerged among participants as a major deterrent for small, diversified, and young farms. Policy design should therefore shift from policing to enabling. At the EU level, simplification can be promoted through plain-language requirements, once-only data submission, and proportional penalties, particularly for minor or unintentional errors. Managing Authorities can institutionalise "compliance via coaching", providing pre-checks and early guidance to prevent errors. More broadly, ring-fenced funds for young and new entrants, women-led holdings, and micro-farms, as well as recognition of multifunctional roles such as education, care, and community services, would target support where it achieves the highest retention and local spill over effects. Managing Authorities and paying agencies should report on simplification and youth/gender targeting as performance indicators in their Strategic Plans.

Environmental ambition must be practical and predictable for farms. Measures should be tailored to farm types and regional conditions, with particular attention to protected and constrained areas, and support should recognise the labour and time required. Participants highlighted reviving soil health, reorienting production systems (for example, towards livestock where calendars are more manageable), and diversification as practical ways to stabilise output and avoid peak workloads. Young farmers in this study were generally supportive of stronger environmental and climate action. However, they emphasised that current measures often increase workload and risk without providing corresponding returns or technical support. Environmental and climate measures should therefore be redesigned. Eligibility rules, payment levels, and monitoring requirements should be explicitly assessed for their impacts on workload, occupational safety and health (OSH) risks, and the viability of small and young farms. Permitting timelines should also be aligned with mandated upgrades.

Research participants emphasised that knowledge, skills, and experience are essential for viable entry and long-term success. They valued learning by doing – spending time on established farms, exposure to different systems, and peer exchange – which they said accelerates confidence and decision-making in the early years. Women highlighted the importance of trusted networks; women-to-women mentoring and peer spaces support both technical work and navigating relationships. Digital tools were discussed ambivalently: they can help, but often increase paperwork and are difficult to integrate into daily routines. The message was that tools should reduce administration and align with actual workflows. Advisory services, vocational education, and peer-to-peer learning therefore need to move beyond narrow technical training. They should include business skills, labour management, work organisation, and mental health. Learning pathways should be co-developed with young farmers, accessible in terms of time and location, and linked to concrete opportunities such as installation support, cooperative initiatives, and leadership roles. Finally, research participants stressed the need to rebuild public understanding of farming; local outreach, including farm-school interactions, was seen as a way to raise the social value attached to farm work.

Research participants described diversification, including value-added processing and direct sales, as a key resilience strategy that enables them to set prices and buffer shocks. They also emphasised localism, community ties, and consumer education as ways to sustain viable outlets and gain recognition. Women participants highlighted educational and social activities as part of broader, community-embedded farm models. Some also mentioned on-farm technologies, such as biogas and solar, as supporting manageability. Together, these narratives link economic stability with diversified, locally rooted farming and closer producer-consumer relationships. Policy should therefore treat diversification not as a residual category but as a deliberate strategy: providing tailored advisory support, adapted financial products and risk-sharing arrangements that enable young farmers to combine economic viability with better work-life balance and more socially valued roles.

Farm renewal is inseparable from territorial justice: young farmers explained that a one-size-fits-all policy overlooks regional constraints and service gaps, particularly in remote and mountain areas with greater distances to markets and weaker rural infrastructure. They called for regionally tailored support and recognition of structural disadvantages in protected sites (e.g. Natura 2000), where obligations are high but compensation is partial or lacking. Across groups, demands for spatial equity – improved access to services, local markets, and fair trading conditions – were linked to making farming viable for young people in underserved regions. These perspectives emphasise that policies must reflect place, not just farm type. Territorial instruments therefore need to be recalibrated to ensure that support for young farmers is integrated into broader rural development and cohesion policies, so that measures reflect place-specific constraints and opportunities rather than a generic “average farm”.

Finally, the report highlights that safety, health, and workload outcomes are policy variables rather than fixed constraints. Investment criteria should explicitly prioritise technologies and practices that reduce labour intensity and injury risk. Replacement services should be

treated as rural infrastructure, not discretionary additions. Systematic collection of near-miss and injury data through advisory services, with feedback into equipment standards and targeted training, would enable learning loops and large-scale prevention. OSH agencies, labour inspectorates and agricultural advisory services should work together to develop preventive, farm-literate approaches that combine training, replacement labour and early-warning systems.

These implications require appropriate governance. Youth and gender mainstreaming should become a routine part of CAP Strategic Plan design, with formal participation by representative organisations and annual reporting on engagement. A concise, policy-relevant set of indicators – such as age and gender distribution in land access, survival of first installations at three, five and eight years, days off taken, uptake of replacement services, injury rates, and mental health service utilisation – would support accountability without placing additional burdens on farms. Rapid-cycle pilots (18–24 months), transparent evaluation, and clear scale-up pathways can turn promising practices into mainstream instruments.

In sum, the analysis recommends rebuilding the enabling environment for new generations of farmers around fair market conditions, lower entry barriers, predictable transfers, parity in social protection, clear rules and advisory-led compliance, achievable environmental ambition, and territorial instruments that make rural life viable for families. If these measures are considered holistically, they will restore agriculture to its rightful place as a dignified, future-oriented profession – economically viable, environmentally credible, and human-centred – capable of attracting, sustaining, and renewing the cohort on which Europe’s food systems depend.

The next section, **ACTIONS NEEDED**, builds on these implications by identifying which drivers of change should be addressed first and by outlining priority policy reforms and audience-specific steps. Together, the implications and actions provide a roadmap from young farmers’ expectations to concrete measures that EU and national authorities, farmer organisations, and researchers can implement over different time horizons.

4.2 Implications in light of the new EU Strategy for Generational Renewal in Agriculture

The conclusions of this study closely align with the European Commission’s new Strategy for Generational Renewal in Agriculture (European Commission 2025a), announced on 21 October 2025, and its accompanying analytical brief on young farmers (European Commission 2025b). Both documents identify demographic ageing, barriers to entry, and persistent income insecurity as central threats to the future of EU farming. The Commission notes that the average age of farm managers has risen to 57 years, with farmers under 40 now representing only about 12% of farm holders and managing a comparatively small share of utilised agricultural area. In response, the strategy sets an aspirational target to double the share of young farmers to 24% by 2040 and proposes that Member States

allocate at least 6% of agricultural spending to generational renewal. This is to be implemented through national strategies covering five areas of action: access to credit and finance, access to knowledge and skills, access to land, resilience and fair living conditions (including new income opportunities), and succession and retirement.

Our qualitative findings provide bottom-up evidence that confirms and deepens this diagnosis. Participants' accounts of structural barriers – high land prices, dependence on family collateral, debt burdens, low and volatile farm incomes, and weak bargaining power in value chains – closely mirror the Commission's identification of constrained access to credit, land, and viable business prospects as key obstacles to entry and expansion for young farmers. The strategy's emphasis on tailored financial instruments, including guarantees, reduced interest rates, and longer repayment periods, as well as the recognition of a growing financing gap of over EUR 14 billion for young farmers, is directly consistent with participants' accounts of limited bank willingness to lend, risk-averse collateral policies, and long-term indebtedness.

Similarly, the strategy's focus on access to land – including the creation of a European Land Observatory, the promotion of land-mobility services, and innovative transfer models – is strongly supported by our results. Young farmers in the focus groups described land as the central bottleneck for both successors and newcomers, with family assets, inheritance, and informal arrangements still decisively shaping who can enter farming and on what terms. Evidence from the analytical brief that young farmers manage a smaller share of owned land and face particular difficulties securing ownership further corroborates these accounts. Our findings therefore reinforce the need for the Commission's proposed land governance tools to be implemented ambitiously at national level, particularly in regions with concentrated ownership, speculative pressures, or protected areas where constraints are high and compensation only partial.

On skills, advisory systems, and learning pathways, the strategy acknowledges that younger generations are more highly trained but still face gaps in applied skills, and proposes to strengthen AKIS, advisory services, peer learning, and programmes such as Erasmus for Young Entrepreneurs and the "Farmers of the Future" best practice pack initiative. Focus group participants' emphasis on learning by doing, women-to-women mentoring, trusted peer networks, and the need for farm-literate advisory support aligns closely with this agenda. At the same time, they express scepticism about digital tools that increase administrative burdens or do not fit daily work routines, indicating that innovation policies and digitalisation efforts must be explicitly designed to reduce complexity rather than add to it.

The strategy's focus on resilience, fair living conditions, and new income opportunities – including farm-relief services, diversification, rural infrastructure, and on-farm renewable energy – also finds strong support in our material. The conclusions highlight that chronic overwork, blurred boundaries between work and home, and the scarcity of replacement

labour create significant risks for health, safety, and well-being, particularly for women. Participants' proposals for cooperative labour pools, replacement-labour vouchers, diversified farm models, and locally rooted value chains directly echo the Commission's call for farm relief services, diversification, and support for renewable energy investments as core elements of a more attractive and resilient farming profession.

This study advances the field by explicitly identifying social protection, mental health, and gender equality as central conditions for generational renewal. While the strategy acknowledges the importance of decent living standards, social services, and pensions – such as through the integration of succession and retirement issues into the European Semester – participants' accounts reveal that gaps in maternity provision, childcare, healthcare, mental health support, and recognition of unpaid family work directly influence decisions to enter, remain in, or leave farming. This indicates that national generational renewal strategies should not only mobilise CAP instruments but also coordinate with social policy reforms to ensure parity with non-farm professions and address the gendered distribution of risks and responsibilities on farms.

The study also addresses CEJA's critical yet constructive response to the strategy (CEJA 2025a). CEJA welcomes the Commission's recognition of young farmers' roles in food security, sustainability, and rural vitality, and supports many of the proposed measures, including the Land Observatory, targeted financial instruments, stronger advisory systems, and attention to social policies. However, it raises strong concerns that (i) the strategy's recommendation to allocate 6% of CAP spending to generational renewal is not reflected as a binding minimum in the legal proposals for the post-2027 CAP, and (ii) reliance on aspirational targets without ring-fenced budgets risks undermining credibility and increasing inequalities between Member States.

These concerns are supported by our findings from the perspective of young farmers. The conclusions show that research participants place high value on predictable, long-term support, clear rules, and advisory-led compliance, and view frequent policy changes, administrative complexity, and uncertainty about future CAP instruments as disincentives to investment and succession. In this respect, the study reinforces CEJA's argument that ambitious generational renewal objectives must be supported by binding financial commitments and robust monitoring, rather than relying solely on guidance and voluntary national uptake.

Finally, research participants' scepticism regarding the emphasis on carbon and nature credits – fearing these schemes may not be accessible or beneficial for smaller farms and young farmers – echoes CEJA's caution that such mechanisms should complement, rather than replace, more direct measures to strengthen primary farm incomes and improve value chains. Their call for fair markets, enforcement of the UTP Directive against unfair trading practices, and public procurement favouring local, diversified production provides a

concrete social and territorial perspective through which the income and resilience objectives of the strategy can be realised.

Taken together, the study's conclusions suggest that the EU Strategy for Generational Renewal in Agriculture is broadly aligned with the priorities identified by young farmers, particularly regarding access to land, finance, skills, and relief services. At the same time, our evidence highlights three areas where implementation will be crucial: (1) securing ring-fenced and adequately targeted resources, as advocated by CEJA; (2) more centrally integrating social protection, mental health, and gender equality into national renewal strategies; and (3) ensuring territorial justice, so that generational renewal policies reflect structural disadvantages in remote, constrained, and protected areas, rather than applying a one-size-fits-all model. In this way, the empirical results provide both support and a critical perspective for the forthcoming design and implementation of EU and national instruments aimed at making farming a viable, dignified, and future-oriented profession for the next generation.

4.3 Methodological considerations and limitations

Sample and recruitment

The achieved sample of 17 participants across five focus groups fell short of the Grant Agreement's indicative target of 30. While smaller than planned, the sample provided strong foundations for qualitative analysis: gender balance (eight women, nine men), representation from ten European countries, and diversity across farm types, sizes, and participant roles. Thematic saturation was reached, with later focus groups reinforcing rather than generating new themes.

Two compositional features have implications for interpretation. First, recruitment through CEJA's network meant participants were predominantly established young farmers with existing organisational connections rather than aspiring new entrants or isolated individuals; only two participants came from non-farming backgrounds. The study therefore captures the perspectives of relatively engaged young farmers rather than those who may have disengaged from farming or its representative structures. Second, the countries not represented — notably Germany, Spain, Romania, Lithuania, and Slovakia — include major agricultural economies. While the pan-European spread achieved enables identification of cross-cutting patterns, findings should not be read as representative of all EU Member States.

Online format and group dynamics

In line with the Grant Agreement, focus groups were conducted online via Zoom given the logistical and financial challenge of convening farmers from across Europe in person. The online format enabled participation from working farms — several participants joined from

agricultural settings — and proved inclusive for young people comfortable with digital communication.

However, the format also imposed constraints. Ninety-minute sessions with four thematic blocks limited depth of discussion on any single topic. Smaller groups (two to five participants) were necessary to ensure all voices were heard within the available time, but this reduced opportunities for debate and disagreement. Language also played a role: with discussions conducted in English, some participants contributed less fluently than others, and the tendency for participants to agree with preceding contributions ("I agree with everything that has been said") may partly reflect linguistic caution rather than genuine consensus.

Analytical approach

This exploratory qualitative study aimed to identify emerging themes and generate transferable insights rather than to achieve statistical representativeness or test hypotheses. The thematic analysis, while systematic, reflects the interpretive orientation of the research team. Exact replicability is not claimed; different analysts might foreground different aspects of the data. The coding process was conducted collaboratively within the ZRC SAZU team, with emerging themes discussed to enhance consistency, though formal inter-coder reliability metrics were not calculated.

Regional comparison across EU member states was not a primary objective and would not be warranted given the sample composition. The findings should be read as illuminating shared concerns and aspirations among young farmers in contemporary Europe, while recognising that national and regional specificities will shape how these play out in particular contexts.

5. Actions Needed

While the previous section outlined broad implications for policy and practice, this section focuses on what needs to be done, by whom, and in what order. It first ranks the main drivers currently undermining the attractiveness of farming and generational renewal, then examines their implications for young people's career decisions, and finally sets out priority policy reforms and audience-specific actions that can be implemented over immediate, medium-term, and long-term timeframes.

The five priority reform areas set out below operationalise the four Key Messages presented in the Executive Summary. Reform Area 1 (market rebalancing) and Reform Area 2 (land access and succession) together implement **Key Message 2** (a fair and predictable operating environment). Reform Area 3 (social protection and care infrastructure) directly implements **Key Message 1** (parity of social rights) and **Key Message 4** (visibility and rights for young women in farming). Reform Areas 4 and 5 (CAP simplification and territorial justice) create the enabling conditions for **Key Message 3** (quality of work and mental well-being) while supporting all other reforms. This architecture ensures that action on any single reform area contributes to multiple policy objectives, reflecting the interconnected nature of the challenges identified by research participants.

MAIN DRIVERS OF CHANGE

1. **Market and income instability in unequal value chains.** Volatile prices, weak bargaining power, and exposure to cheap imports are the most immediate and destabilising forces shaping young people's employment prospects in farming. Without predictable incomes, neither new entrants nor successors can commit to long-term investment or decent working conditions.
2. **Access to land, capital, and succession pathways.** Inflated land prices, reliance on family collateral, and informal transfer routes make entry and expansion highly selective. These factors privilege those with assets and male succession norms, while excluding women, newcomers, and farms in structurally disadvantaged areas.
3. **Social protection gaps, workload, and health risks.** The absence of robust maternity and paternity cover, sickness replacement, and mental health support – combined with long hours, seasonal peaks, and normalised overwork – erodes the sustainability of farming as a life project, especially for young families.
4. **Policy complexity and misalignment between ambition and implementation.** Administrative burdens, fragmented instruments, and inconsistent rules (for example, between environmental and livestock regulations) turn policy from an enabling framework into a risk factor, particularly for small, diversified, and young farms.
5. **Territorial inequalities and uneven access to infrastructure and skills.** Remote, mountain, and protected areas face higher costs, weaker services, and fewer market outlets, despite high environmental obligations. Limited access to training, digital infrastructure, and peer networks amplifies these spatial injustices.

Across these drivers, climate change and technological advances act as cross-cutting multipliers: they intensify existing vulnerabilities where enabling institutions are absent, but can improve resilience when paired with fair markets, land access, and social protection. Taken together, these drivers indicate where policy interventions will have the greatest leverage: stabilising farm-level incomes, opening inclusive land and succession pathways, closing social protection gaps, simplifying implementation, and reducing territorial inequalities.

IMPLICATIONS FOR THE ATTRACTIVENESS OF FARMING AND GENERATIONAL RENEWAL

- **Farming remains aspirational but not reliably viable.** Young people are attracted by autonomous, meaningful, environmentally responsible work, yet are discouraged by unstable incomes, heavy workloads, and weak social rights.
- **Entry and continuity are increasingly selective.** Those without family assets, or who are women, newcomers, or in marginal regions, face disproportionately higher risks. In practice, “choosing” farming is only feasible for a narrowing group.
- **Work-life imbalance is a central deterrent.** The difficulty of taking time off, raising children, caring for elders, or managing health without jeopardising the farm makes agriculture less attractive than non-farm professions with clearer rights and entitlements.
- **The gap between policy rhetoric and lived reality undermines trust.** When environmental and social ambitions are not matched by practical support, predictable rules, and fair returns, young farmers interpret this gap as a signal that their future in agriculture is precarious rather than protected.

Taken together, these dynamics mean that attractiveness is less about image and more about the credibility of a long-term livelihood promise. Where that promise is not credible, generational renewal stalls and rural employment becomes more fragile.

PRIORITY POLICY REFORMS (TOP LEVERS TO IMPLEMENT THE KEY MESSAGES)

The following five reform areas implement the Key Messages by specifying where EU and national policymakers should focus their efforts in the short and medium term.

1. Rebalance markets in favour of farm-level income security

- Strengthen and enforce Unfair Trading Practices rules.
- Promote cost-of-production reference tools and standard contract clauses to secure predictable margins.
- Use public procurement and territorial quality schemes to create stable outlets for local, diversified, and women-led farms.

2. Unlock inclusive land access and succession pathways

- Scale up land-mobility instruments (land-matching, tax incentives for early transfer, pre-emption rights, lease facilitation).

- Prioritise guarantees and working capital support over collateral-based loans in start-up finance.
- Institutionalise “succession clinics” combining legal, financial, and psychosocial counselling, with explicit attention to gender equality and non-family entrants.

3. Achieve parity in social protection and care infrastructure

- Introduce maternity and paternity leave, sickness cover with replacement services, and pension rules that recognise unpaid family labour.
- Integrate mental health support and farm-literate counselling into advisory systems.
- Treat replacement labour schemes and childcare as core rural infrastructure.

4. Simplify and repurpose CAP and national instruments as enabling systems

- Reduce administrative complexity through plain-language rules, once-only data submission, and proportional penalties.
- Shift towards “compliance via coaching”: pre-checks, advisory support, and early guidance instead of ex post punishment.
- Ring-fence funding for young and new entrants, women-led farms, and micro-holdings, recognising their multifunctional roles.

5. Embed territorial justice and safety/health outcomes in rural policy design

- Design regionally tailored measures for remote, mountain, and protected areas, with compensation that matches obligations.
- Prioritise investments and technologies that demonstrably reduce labour intensity and injury risk.
- Use a concise indicator set (age/gender in land access, survival of new installations, days off, injury, and mental health indicators) to hold systems accountable.

5.1 Audience-specific actions and recommendations

The following audience-specific actions translate the priority reforms into concrete, tactical steps for the SafeHabitus consortium, EU and national policymakers, farmer organisations, and researchers.

5.1.1. SAFEHABITUS PROJECT

Use of this report (D4.3) to guide future project activities:

For Task 4.3 – translation of OSH and well-being good practices (GP)

- Use focus group findings to identify priority themes for transferring OSH and well-being practices: workload and time pressure, lack of replacement labour, mental health strain, gendered divisions of labour, gaps in advisory services and social protection, and territorial inequalities.

- Select and sequence GPs that address these challenges in young farmers' daily lives, avoiding generic "one-size-fits-all" solutions.
- Define success and learning outcomes beyond accident reduction to include perceived stress, work-life balance, ability to take time off, recognition of unpaid work (especially by women and family members), and confidence to discuss OSH and well-being.

For WP6 policy brief – "Enhancing the social sustainability and attractiveness of farming"

- Use concrete focus group examples – short supply chains, community-supported models, on-farm social and educational activities, women-led diversification – as social innovation case studies in the policy brief and European Policy Forum for Farm Health and Safety (EPF) discussions.
- Highlight structural constraints identified in D4.3—chronic overwork, lack of replacement labour, mental health pressures, unpaid and gendered work, weak social protection, and territorial inequalities – as boundary conditions for successful social innovation.
- Translate these implications into a small set of policy entry points and social indicators (e.g. rest time, work-life balance, perceived stress) that complement traditional OSH metrics.

For the SafeHabitus hackathon and D4.4 – pathways to futures that support well-being

- Design the hackathon challenge to take account of the constellation of challenges rather than focusing on a single challenge. It is recognised that this will create methodological challenges and hence, in line with the findings presented above, we recommend that the overarching framework for the hackathon is focused on climate-related OSH risks.
- Bring together farmers, policymakers, OSH specialists, researchers, and civil society (with strong participation from women and young people) to co-create solutions that strengthen social protection, replacement labour, access to land and finance, and rural infrastructure.
- Organise work around several challenge areas, e.g. (1) climate uncertainty and OSH risks; (2) the social dimension of agricultural work (social security, mental health support, territorial justice).

5.1.2. POLICYMAKERS (EU / national)

Immediate reforms (within 1 year)

Stabilise incomes and reduce immediate risk

- Introduce or expand emergency income-stabilisation tools targeted at young and new entrants.

- Strengthen enforcement of Unfair Trading Practices and publish clear, farmer-oriented guidance on complaint mechanisms.

Lower the administrative barrier to entry

- Establish “one-stop shop” helpdesks or digital portals for young and new entrants, providing integrated support on CAP, taxation and labour law.
- Simplify core application forms (start-up aid, small investment grants) and align deadlines with farming calendars.
- Signal commitment to social protection
- Pilot replacement labour schemes and targeted childcare support in regions with high proportions of young farmers.
- Initiate legal reviews to identify regulatory gaps in maternity, paternity, sickness and accident coverage for farmers and farm workers.

Medium-term reforms (2–5 years)

Re-design support around the life-course needs of young farmers

- Integrate social protection modules (pensions, health, care) into CAP Strategic Plans and national rural programmes.
- Scale up land-mobility mechanisms (land banks, fiscal incentives for early transfer, support for non-family succession).

Align environmental, food and rural policies

- Link environmental and climate measures with long-term contracts and price guarantees for public goods provision.
- Use public procurement to anchor local markets for sustainable, small-scale and young farmers' products.

Institutionalise safety, health and mental well-being

- Incorporate labour safety and mental health indicators into monitoring frameworks.
- Fund regionally appropriate replacement labour, respite schemes and counselling services.

Long-term reforms (5+ years)

Rebalance value chains structurally

- Support cooperative and farmer-owned processing, logistics and retail structures that retain value in rural areas.
- Promote long-term interprofessional agreements that share risks and value between farmers, processors and retailers.

Secure intergenerational, gender-just land regimes

- Reform inheritance, tenancy and land taxation to prevent excessive concentration and support intergenerational, gender-equal transfer of holdings.
- Consolidate land-use planning to protect agricultural land, especially in peri-urban and high-quality production areas.

Normalise parity of social rights in agriculture

- Progress towards full parity of social rights for farmers and farm workers with other self-employed and employed groups.
- Institutionalise ongoing youth and gender mainstreaming in all rural and agricultural legislation, including mandatory participation of representative organisations.

5.1.3. FARMER ORGANISATIONS

Mentoring and peer support

- Establish structured mentoring schemes pairing experienced farmers with young entrants and successors, with targeted outreach to women and newcomers.
- Create peer-learning groups (e.g. “succession circles”, “new entrants clubs”) that address both technical and psychosocial aspects of farming careers.

Mental health and well-being

- Integrate mental health as a standard topic in advisory services, training, and farmer meetings.
- Partner with health services and NGOs to offer confidential counselling and crisis support tailored to farming realities.
- Normalise conversations about stress, burnout, and family conflict in succession processes, reducing stigma.

Cooperative and collective models

- Promote cooperative purchasing, marketing, and processing to strengthen bargaining power and stabilise prices for young and small farmers.
- Support shared machinery pools, labour-sharing, and service cooperatives to reduce workload peaks and investment pressure.
- Encourage cooperative childcare or care-sharing initiatives (e.g. between neighbouring farms), especially in remote areas.

Advocacy and representation

- Ensure meaningful representation of young farmers, women, and newcomers in organisational governance and negotiation structures.

- Use evidence from mentoring, mental health, and cooperative initiatives to advocate for supportive public policies.

5.1.4. RESEARCHERS

Future quantitative and longitudinal studies

- Develop **longitudinal panel studies** that follow cohorts of young farmers and new entrants over time to track their trajectories, exits, and well-being outcomes.
- Produce **quantitative evidence** on the impacts of land mobility schemes, social protection reforms, and cooperative models on farm survival, quality of work, and gender equality.
- Integrate **psychosocial and health indicators** (stress, mental health, work-life balance, injury) into existing farm structure and income surveys.
- Conduct **territorially sensitive analyses** distinguishing remote, mountain, peri-urban, and intensive regions to capture spatial injustices.
- **Co-design research** with farmer organisations and policymakers so that results feed directly into the refinement of instruments and monitoring frameworks.

The evidence delivers a clear message:

Without coordinated action by policymakers, farmer organisations, and researchers to stabilise incomes, open up land and succession, and secure full social protection, generational renewal in European agriculture will stall. Farming will then shift from a potential driver of just, sustainable rural futures to a source of increasing precarity and social inequality.

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7. Appendices

APPENDIX 1: TOPICS AND QUESTIONS OF THE FOCUS GROUPS

THEME I: INSIGHTS FROM YOUNG FARMERS

The context - the rules of the game - in which farmers operate is constantly changing, e.g. in the face of technological progress, administrative and normative requirements, market fluctuations, weather conditions, public demands on food quality, environmental protection, etc., which pose them with certain challenges and demands for action.

1. How do you see your current position as a farmer in this changing agricultural context?

Research has identified several trends that affect agriculture today and will most likely continue to influence it in the future, e.g. climate change, environmental degradation, growing world population and global demand for food, advances in new technologies (digitalisation and biotechnology), changing values in society, international situation (conflicts, wars), general and agricultural policies developments, etc.

2. In your opinion, what are the most urgent trends influencing agriculture today and how will they affect the future of farming?

3. How (if) will these trends and changes affect your career as a farmer or your decision to become a farmer?

4. Do these changes affect your mental health and your work-life balance?

THEME II: GENERATIONAL RENEWAL

As outlined in the recent reform of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), one of the biggest challenges for the agricultural sector is generational renewal, as the agricultural labour force is ageing dramatically and a large proportion of EU farmers will retire in the coming years, while the proportion of young farmers, especially women, is worryingly low.

5. What conditions must be met (e.g. barriers addressed) and what strategies need to be implemented on the farm for you to take over the farm/to start the career in farming? What needs to be done in other areas, e.g. in the community, society or elsewhere?

6. In your opinion, what should a successful young farmer who takes over a farm, look like, what qualities should they have?

7. What status should the farmer who takes over the farm have; can it be a part-time farmer or a full-time farmer or a hobby farmer or something else? What are your personal priorities in this regard?

8. How can young people be encouraged to take up a farming career? Should genders be considered equally, or should e.g. women be approached differently, with special incentives?

9. What should the farm you want to pass on to the next generation look like?

THEME III: FUTURE CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

Various unfavourable statistics on fatal and non-fatal injuries and suicide rates among farmers in the EU show that working conditions in agriculture are also highly problematic from a health and safety point of view. Farm work is inherently physically demanding and strenuous. Farmers have to work long hours, adapt to the needs of the animals, the planting season and the harvest, and are exposed to extreme weather conditions. In addition, the farming lifestyle, where the workplace is neither a home nor separate from the home, also affects farmers' quality of life.

10. In your opinion, what factors other than those mentioned shape working conditions in agriculture the most?

11. What factors will influence working conditions in agriculture in the future and how (positively/negatively)?

12. What changes do you personally experience in working environment and how do they affect your health and safety?

THEME IV: POLICY NEEDS

In previous programming periods, the EU CAP and national agricultural policies have focused on issues and implemented measures mainly aimed at developing and implementing standards for sufficient and safe food production, improving production technologies, preserving and protecting the environment, improving farmers' knowledge in production, marketing and entrepreneurial skills, etc., and have provided subsidies and support for these purposes. The research funding under the EU CAP has also been invested in projects that contribute to agronomic, technological, environmental and economic goals and solutions. Due to the current critical labour shortage in agriculture, agricultural policy makers are now also focusing more and more on the social dimension of agriculture.

13. What issues and questions do you think the current EU CAP and national agricultural policies should focus on in the coming years to improve the situation in agriculture in terms of labour and quality of life, especially to attract young farmers to a career in agriculture?

14. What priority do you think should be given to meeting the social needs of farmers, (e.g. social security and pensions, access to health and care services (e.g. childcare), the right to rest/holidays, opportunities to reconcile work and family life, etc.)?

15. What specific initiatives and measures do you think should be prioritised to support young farmers and promote sustainable development in agriculture?

16. How can existing CAP measures, such as top-ups and targeted support, be enhanced to support sustainable development and reduce barriers to entry for young farmers?

APPENDIX 2: Key CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PARTICIPANTS

Table 3: Key Characteristics of Focus Group Participants

FG	Participant Gender Education	Country	Farm Type / Size & Scope	Role & Status
FG1	#1 / F / good education	AT	Pig breeding, arable crops, forest (5 ha) / Other not specified	Co-manager on in-laws' farm (now on maternity leave) & CEJA member
FG1	#2 / F / 8-year experience	IT	Organic vegetables, vineyard, pumpkins (40 ha) / Other not specified	Farmer on her family farm
FG1	#3 / F / univ. educated	SI	Apples (Natura 2000) / Not specified	Part-time employed on brother's and parents' family farm, part-time off-farm work & CEJA member
FG1	#4 / F / MSc student	IE	Heifer rearing (contract/dairy-linked) / Not specified	Joint operator on father's farm, full-time gov. worker
FG1	#5 / M / univ. educated	PT	Cherries, vineyards, orchards / Medium size	Farmer on his family farm and technician
FG2	#6 / M	IE	Dairy / Not specified	Farmer in partnership with parents & Agrifairers member (young farmers in IE)
FG2	#7 / M	UK	Livestock (forage-based) / Not specified	Core operator
FG3	#8 / M	BE	Dairy, beef, cereals / Not specified	Moving in co-ownership with his father & active in FJA, CEJA

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FG3	#9 / F	AT	Dairy, beef, arable crops / Not specified	Co-operator on parents' farm,
FG4	#10 / M / 14-year experience	EE	Conventional grain farm / 300 ha	Owner-operator
FG4	#11 / M / 2-year in NZ	FR	Organic beef / 150 heads, 150 ha	Full-time farmer, working together with father and uncle
FG4	#12 / M / 6-year experience, 3-4 months in NZ	FR	Conventional dairy, crops, biogas / 120 heads	Moving in co-ownership with his father
FG5	#13 / M / Animal science student	PL	Dairy farm/ 150 head including young stock	Farmer on parents' farm
FG5	#14 / F / Medicine	SI	Dairy, milk value-added products / 130 head including young stock	Full-time farmer (now on maternity leave)
FG5	#15 / F / MA of animal science	SI	Pig breeding / 30–40 sows	Takes initiative on a parents' farm
FG5	#16 / M / Student of agriculture	PL	Pigs, traditional mixing farming / Not specified	Works on uncle's pig & grandfather's farm
FG5	#17 / F / univ. educated in ag	PL	Cereals and field bean / Not specified	Works on parents' family farm

APPENDIX 3: FOCUS GROUP SCENARIO – MODERATOR GUIDE AND INFORMED CONSENT FORM

The focus groups were conducted online via ZOOM videoconference and lasted approximately **90 minutes**. Each group was planned to **include 4–6 participants**, a moderator, and a co-moderator. The moderator guided the discussion, while the co-moderator took notes, monitored time, and managed technical issues.

The focus group scenario was structured in four main phases:

1. **Welcome, introduction and ethical information**
2. **Participant introductions**
3. **Thematic discussion (Themes I–IV)**
4. **Closing and thanks**

The **detailed guiding questions** used for each theme are presented in **Appendix 1** and are therefore **not repeated** here. Appendix 3 instead outlines the structure, flow and content of the focus group sessions.

1. Welcome, introduction and ethical information (approx. 10 minutes)

The informal consent form sent to invited participants prior to the focus group discussions is attached at the end of this appendix. The moderator welcomed participants, thanked them for their willingness to participate and briefly introduced the *SafeHabitus* project and the purpose of the focus groups. The introduction highlighted that:

- the project aims to contribute to safer, healthier and more attractive farming across Europe,
- the focus groups are intended to better understand how young farmers view their current situation, future prospects, and policy needs, and
- the findings will be used in anonymised form in project reports and publications, targeted at policy makers and the wider public.

The moderator then briefly introduced herself (and the co-moderator), including institutional affiliation and role in the project (e.g. Work Package 4 leader), and noted her long-standing interest in and familiarity with farming life.

Ethical and practical aspects were explained, including:

- voluntary participation and the right to withdraw at any time without consequences,
- confidentiality and anonymisation of contributions in all outputs,
- secure handling of any personal data,
- audio (and, where applicable, video) recording of the session for research purposes only, and

- approximate duration and structure of the discussion.

Participants were invited to ask questions for clarification before proceeding.

2. Participant introductions (approx. 10 minutes)

Participants were then asked to briefly introduce themselves, including:

- their name, country and region,
- their current involvement in farming (e.g. farm manager, successor, family helper, aspiring entrant),
- key farm characteristics (e.g. main production orientation, size, type of family involvement), and
- whether they currently see themselves as intending to remain in, enter, or potentially exit farming in the future.

This short round served both as an ice-breaker and as a way to situate their subsequent contributions.

3. Thematic discussion (Themes I–IV) (approx. 65 minutes)

The core of the focus group consisted of four thematic blocks. Each theme was allocated approximately **15–20 minutes**. The moderator introduced each theme with a short contextual statement and then used the guiding questions listed in **Appendix 1** to facilitate discussion.

Theme I – Insights from young farmers

Theme II – Generational renewal

Theme III – Future challenges and opportunities

Theme IV – Policy needs

Throughout the thematic discussion, the moderator ensured that all participants had the opportunity to speak, encouraged interaction among them, and, where necessary, probed for clarification, examples and divergent viewpoints.

4. Closing and thanks (approx. 5 minutes)

In the final phase, the moderator briefly summarised the main points emerging from the discussion and invited participants to add any **final comments, reflections or issues** they considered important but had not yet been addressed.

Participants were thanked for their time, openness and valuable insights, and were informed about the **next steps** in the project, including the planned use of the data (e.g. in analytical reports and policy briefs) and, where applicable, how they might be informed about key results.

An example of informal consent distributed to the participants prior to the focus group discussion:

INFORMED CONSENT FOR DATA COLLECTION DURING THE FOCUS GROUP

recorded as part of the online event “**SafeHabitus Focus Group on the Future of Farming**” held on ZOOM on **10 February 2025** by Majda Črnič Istenič and Mateja Slovenc Grasselli from the Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts as a contribution to the research activities of the SafeHabitus project.

I, **the undersigned**,

Hereby confirm that

I have been informed of the objectives of the focus group and consent to the processing of the data provided during it for the purposes explained to me in advance.

I understand that my participation is voluntary, that the data can only be used for the specific purposes of the project as explained to me and for no other purpose and that it will never be shared with any external party and that my identity will not be revealed under any circumstances.

I am aware that I can withdraw at any time without giving reasons and I know that in the event of withdrawal, all personal data that I have provided up to that point will be deleted, unless I agree otherwise.

Date: _____

Signature: _____

APPENDIX 4: CODING TABLES (I-IV)

Table 4: Coding Table of Theme I (The changing agricultural context)

Emerging theme	Working code	Operational definition	Primary Q(s)	Related
1. Structural challenges & economic precarity	ECON-PRECARITY	Economic instability due to volatile prices, high input and land costs, bureaucratic burden, import competition (e.g., MERCOSUR); and weak bargaining power in the supply chain.	Q1, Q2, Q3	POLICY-TRUST, SUCCESSION, MENTAL HEALTH, LABOUR-SHORTAGE, RESILIENCE-INNOV
2. Generational transition & farm succession	SUCCESSION	Uncertainty about taking over farms, long investment horizons, retirement timing, and risk from shifting policy/market contexts.	Q1, Q2, Q3	DIGITAL-DIVIDE, POLICY-TRUST, ECON-PRECARITY, MENTAL HEALTH
3. Labour shortage & workforce sustainability	LABOUR-SHORTAGE	Difficulty finding/retaining skilled and general labour; reliance on family/part-time work; unattractive conditions.	Q1, Q2	MENTAL HEALTH, ECON-PRECARITY, RESILIENCE-INNOV
4. Climate change & environmental adaptation	CLIMATE-ADAPT	Direct experiences of changing weather, shortened/erratic seasons, pests/diseases, and misalignment of regulations with new climatic realities.	Q1, Q2	POLICY-TRUST, RESILIENCE-INNOV
5. Digitalization & technological disparities	DIGITAL-DIVIDE	Opportunities from precision/AI/automation vs. barriers from poor connectivity and	Q1, Q2	RESILIENCE-INNOV, POLICY-TRUST, SUCCESSION

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		generational gaps in digital skills.		
6. Gender & the evolving role of women	GENDER-ROLE	Women bringing diversified, socially oriented models while facing recognition and finance barriers.	Q1	RESILIENCE-INNOV, POLICY-TRUST
7. Policy disillusionment & loss of trust	POLICY-TRUST	Perceptions of unstable, incoherent EU/national policy (e.g., Green Deal shifts, CAP rules, trade deals) and punitive compliance culture.	Q2, Q3	ECON-PRECARITY, MENTAL HEALTH, SUCCESSION, DIGITAL-DIVIDE, GENDER-ROLE, CLIMATE-ADAPT, RESILIENCE-INNOV
8. Mental health & work-life balance	MENTAL HEALTH	Burnout, pressure, isolation, especially among part-time farmers juggling multiple jobs and compliance burdens.	Q4 (also Q1-Q3)	LABOUR-SHORTAGE, RESILIENCE-INNOV, ECON-PRECARITY, POLICY-TRUST, SUCCESSION
9. Resilience & innovation amid uncertainty	RESILIENCE-INNOV	Coping strategies: diversification, direct sales, value-adding, and entrepreneurial tech solutions to maintain autonomy and income.	Q1, Q2, Q3	ECON-PRECARITY, MENTAL HEALTH, LABOUR-SHORTAGE, CLIMATE-ADAPT, GENDER-ROLE, DIGITAL-DIVIDE

Legend: Primary Q(s): main focus group question(s) where the theme appears most strongly.

Table 5: Coding Table of Theme II (Generational change)

Emerging theme	Working code	Operational definition	Primary Q(s)	Related
1. Tension Between Tradition and Innovation	TRAD-INNOV	Negotiation between respecting legacy (identity, practices, inheritance routines) and introducing technological, ecological, and organisational change by successors.	Q5, Q9	EMOTIONS, ASPIRATIONS, UNCERTAINTY, LEARNING
2. Structural Inequities and Gatekeeping	STRUCT	Unequal access to land, credit, policy benefits, and knowledge; bureaucratic hurdles that favour insiders (family-tied, male) and disadvantage newcomers/women.	Q5, Q8, Q9	LEARNING, IMAGINARY, ASPIRATIONS
3. Emotional Labour and Psychological Readiness	EMOTIONS	Relational and identity work involved in succession; stigma around help-seeking; need for advisory and psychological services alongside technical/economic support.	Q5, Q9	TRAD-INNOV, ASPIRATIONS
4. The Social Imaginary of Farming	IMAGINARY	Cultural narratives and public perception shaping pride, legitimacy, and recruitment; strategies to 'reclaim the story' via schools, community, and social media.	Q5, Q8	STRUCT, ASPIRATIONS
5. The Uncertainty of the Future	UNCERTAINTY	Climate, market and policy volatility that create existential doubts and uneven resilience; need for	Q5, Q9	TRAD-INNOV and ASPIRATIONS

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		adaptability and optionality in farm design.		
6. Learning and Knowledge Flows	LEARNING	Bridging gaps between theory and practice, generations, and insider/outsider pathways; making practical, land-based training and mentorship accessible.	Q5, Q9	STRUCT, TRAD-INNOV
7. Aspirational Models for the Future Farm	ASPIRATIONS	Shared vision for economically viable, modern, sustainable, and family-friendly farms; technology and design choices to support dignity and balance.	Q5, Q9	UNCERTAINTY, STRUCT, TRAD-INNOV, IMAGINARY, EMOTIONS

Table 6: Coding table of Theme III (Improving working environment)

Emerging theme	Working code	Operational definition	Primary Q(s)	Related
1. Work–Life Balance & Mental Health	WLB	Struggles to balance farm work with private/family life; stress, loneliness, anxiety; seasonal overload and off-season underload; lack of structured time off and replacement services.	Q10, Q11, Q12	SOCIAL PERC, ECON, TECH, LABOUR, GENDER
2. Gender, Family Dynamics & Invisible Labour	GENDER	Gendered division of labour, maternity/parental leave challenges, unpaid/invisible work by family members, and the emotional/relational strain of co-working with family.	Q10, Q12	WLB, LABOUR, ECON,
3. Technological Modernisation (Robotics, Digitalisation, AI) – Ambivalences	TECH	Adoption of robots, sensors, drones, AI to reduce physical strain and labour scarcity; concerns about costs, reliability, skills gaps, and over-reliance.	Q11, Q12	LABOUR, WLB, ECON
4. Labour Shortage & Succession Crisis	LABOUR	Difficulty attracting/retaining seasonal and permanent workers; ageing workforce; reluctance of youth to enter physically demanding and low-status farm work; implications for farm scale and continuity.	Q10, Q11	TECH, ECON, SOCIAL PERC, WLB, GENDER
5. Social Perception, Bureaucracy & Moral Pressure	SOCIAL PERC	Pressure from public scrutiny (e.g., animal NGOs), stigma toward certain sectors, administrative burden and policy volatility; feelings of distrust and identity threat.	Q10, Q11	ECON, LABOUR, WLB

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<p>6. Economic Fragility, CAP Dependence & 7. Investment Risk</p>	<p>ECON</p>	<p>Low income and price pressure; dependence on CAP and national supports; high and risky investments for modernisation; links between income and safety/health outcomes.</p>	<p>Q10, Q11</p>	<p>TECH, LABOUR, GENDER, WLB, SOCIAL PERC</p>
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Table 7: Coding Table of Theme IV (Policy needs)

Emerging theme	Working code	Operational definition	Primary Q(s)	Related
1. Structural & financial barriers to entry and generational renewal	ENTRY-BARRIERS	Barriers to starting, taking over, or expanding farms; access to land/capital, succession hurdles, high start-up costs; calls for start-up aid, risk-sharing, and smoother extra-familial transfers.	Q13, Q16	RURAL-INFRA, CAP-SIMPLIFY, MARKET-STABILITY
2. Uncertain markets & need for economic stability	MARKET-STABILITY	Desire for stable, fair prices and predictable markets; scepticism toward subsidies as substitutes for functioning value chains.	Q13, Q16	ENTRY-BARRIERS, CAP-SIMPLIFY, FARM-IMAGE, TRADE-STANDARDS
3. Clearer, simpler & better-targeted CAP	CAP-SIMPLIFY	Overload from bureaucracy, opacity of rules, one-size-fits-all measures; call for simplification and clearer, tailored instruments for small/young farms and specific territories.	Q13	SOCIAL-RIGHTS, RURAL-INFRA, ENTRY-BARRIERS, MARKET-STABILITY, ECO-COMPENSATION
4. Social infrastructure, work-life balance & support services	SOCIAL-RIGHTS	Social security parity (pensions, maternity/parental leave), healthcare/mental-health access, replacement labour, childcare; visibility of women's work and entitlements.	Q14	RURAL-INFRA, CAP-SIMPLIFY, FARM-IMAGE
5. Ecological frustration & under-compensation	ECO-COMPENSATION	Tension between environmental obligations and insufficient remuneration, especially in protected areas; eco-	Q13, Q16	RURAL-INFRA, CAP-SIMPLIFY, FARM-IMAGE, TRADE-STANDARDS,

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		schemes perceived as partial-cost coverage.		MARKET-STABILITY
6. Territorial cohesion & rural infrastructure	RURAL-INFRA	Distance to markets/services, uneven rural services (health, transport, education, digital); need for balanced regional development to retain/attract youth.	Q13	SOCIAL-RIGHTS, FARM-IMAGE, CAP-SIMPLIFY, ECO-COMPENSATION, ENTRY-BARRIERS
7. Cultural recognition & public perception of farming	FARM-IMAGE	Misunderstanding of farming work and value; call for public campaigns, food literacy, school-farm links; rebuilding social legitimacy and pride.	Q13	SOCIAL-RIGHTS, RURAL-INFRA, ECO-COMPENSATION, MARKET-STABILITY, TRADE-STANDARDS
8. Trade & standards: MERCOSUR criticism and 'European quality food'	TRADE-STANDARDS	Perceived contradictions between EU sustainability goals and trade deals; desire to protect EU standards and local producers.	Q13	FARM-IMAGE, ECO-COMPENSATION, MARKET-STABILITY

APPENDIX 5: DETAILED RESULTS

After the first reading of all focus group transcripts, we decided to start the thematic analysis with a discussion that developed around **question 9** (Theme II): ***What should the farm you would like to pass on to the next generation look like?*** Firstly, this discussion reflects the young farmers' vision of a good farmer, in which they refer to both "the production roles and the wider social and moral roles of the good farmer" (Burton et al. 2021: 8). Secondly, this discussion forms the basis for our thematic analysis, as several interconnected themes have emerged that express both the shared **concerns** and **hopes** of European farmers about the future of their farms.

Table 8: Ideal Farm to Pass On

Feature	Description
Financially Sound	Debt-free, profitable, with fair income potential
Modern and Automated	Efficient machinery, technology-integrated, physically less taxing
Environmentally Responsible	Sustainable practices, climate-resilient, low emissions
Emotionally Supportive	Encourages family collaboration and intergenerational respect
Socially Secured	... As any other job
Flexible	Freedom to innovate or reorient the business (autonomy)
Customer-Connected	Strong community ties and supply chain relations
Free from Stresses and Uncertainties	... That research participants are going through now

A prevalent theme is the desire for future farms to be **economically viable and structurally modern**. Participants emphasised the importance of having modern equipment, infrastructure and financial stability. These elements are seen as prerequisites for a sustainable and attractive farm transfer. Participant #9 (AT) emphasised that the infrastructure of farms should not be older than 15 years to ensure that they remain feasible with current income levels. Similarly, #4 (IE) and #17 (PL) emphasised the value of safety, efficiency and modernisation. The emphasis was not on opulence, but on maintaining functional and effective operating standards that allow the farm to remain competitive and liveable.

Sustainability was repeatedly emphasised, both in ecological and socio-economic terms. Participants were concerned about environmental degradation and climate change and sought the transfer of farms that are both productive and environmentally responsible. Participants #10 (EE) and #2 (IT) linked innovation and environmental care, while #14 (SI) aimed for a “sustainable and nature-friendly” farm. These descriptions indicate that environmental awareness is deeply woven into the vision of the future and is in line with general political trends in Europe.

The importance of respectful **co-operation between the generations** was discussed in almost all groups. The envisioned farm is not only a productive space, but also a legacy of the family and the community continuity. Participants emphasised that farm succession should honour the past while allowing for innovation and adaptation. Participants #11 (FR) and #8 (BE), for example, talked about the challenges and the need to bridge generational perspectives. Their accounts show that succession needs to be both collaborative and adaptable, allowing younger generations to bring in new ideas while respecting the efforts of older generations.

The participants expressed a strong desire to improve the **quality of life** and **work-life balance** for future farmers. Long working hours, psycho-physical stress and economic uncertainty were cited as burdens that the next generation will hopefully not inherit. Instead, they would like a farm with “equal social security as any other job” (#14, SI). Participants #2 (IT) and #6 (IE) were particularly vocal about the low quality of life farmers currently experience and emphasised the importance of building a farm that provides a fair income and social stability. This theme was often accompanied by a vision of farms utilising automation and reducing physical workload, as seen in participant #13’s (PL) comments about avoiding the physical toll he experienced.

The issue of **flexibility** – both in terms of farm structure and strategic orientation – was strongly articulated. Farmers envision a future in which farms can adapt to changing socio-economic, environmental, and personal conditions. **Freedom** for the next generation to **choose their own path** was mentioned as a nuanced but important theme. Many participants, such as #12 (FR) and #15 (SI), spoke of the importance of voluntary succession and the freedom to innovate or even leave the profession, rather than viewing farming as an inherited duty. This reflects a shift away from purely duty-bound intergenerational transfers towards a more open, identity-based understanding of farming as a life choice and vocation.

The vision of a **customer-centred farm** with strong community ties and integrated supply chain relationships is another important overarching theme in the focus group discussions. This theme reflects a broader aspiration to see farms not as isolated production units, but as embedded socio-economic hubs that interact meaningfully with consumers, communities and food systems. Participant #2 (IT) articulated this vision most clearly, emphasising the importance of a “great relationship with the customer” and with “all the people that create the chain.” For her, a desirable future farm includes not only physical infrastructure, but also a network of meaningful relationships – with consumers, processors and retailers – that

support both economic and emotional sustainability. This view reflects a shift from traditional productivist farming models to community-based and relationship-oriented agriculture. It is in line with contemporary agri-food paradigms that emphasise transparency, traceability, and local food systems.

The longing for **a farm free from stress, pressure, and uncertainty** emerged in the focus groups as a profound sub-theme that ran through the discussions on economic viability, sustainability, and intergenerational transfer. This theme reflects a deep desire to not only modernise or preserve farms, but to transform the experience of farming into one that promotes mental, emotional, and social well-being. For example, #6 (IE) said directly that he does not want the next generation “to have to go through all the stress and uncertainties that we’re going through now” and that he wonders if there is even a future for him in farming under the current conditions. Similarly, #4 (IE) hopes that the future generation “won’t have to worry about all the things we worry about,” including economic unpredictability, climate change, and political instability. The desire to alleviate these burdens reveals a quest not only for financial sustainability, but also for emotional relief and life satisfaction. The longing for a stress-free, secure agricultural future is a unifying theme in these discussions. It transcends national and generational boundaries and reflects a deep-rooted desire to pass on not only land and machinery, but also a better life – one in which the next generation can thrive, not just survive.

The participants emphasise that today’s uncertainties are fuelling fears about the future of agriculture and raising doubts about long-term sustainability. However, their hopes are centred on a farm structure in which knowledge sharing, innovation, emotional well-being and work-life balance take the place of stress and exhaustion. To summarise, while the farm of the future should be technologically equipped and ecologically adaptable, its most compelling feature is its ability to alleviate the mental and physical pressures that have long plagued the profession. **The farm of tomorrow** is not only a productive enterprise, but also a resilient and nurturing legacy that not only provides a livelihood for its successors, but also enables them to live in dignity. In the words of the research participants, it is important to leave a legacy of mental well-being for the next generation.

In line with the dual message of hope and concern that emerged from the focus group discussions on question 9, we decided to organise the thematic analysis into three interrelated dimensions: 1) the **key** messages of the **emerging themes**, 2) the **pressures and stresses** (challenges) addressed, and 3) **the hopes** (anticipated solutions) discussed in each theme (I–IV), as shown below. The latter two dimensions (pressures and stresses and hopes) are summarised in the main text, while the enriched version (with quotes) can be found in **APPENDIX 5**.

THEME I (FARMERS’ INSIGHTS INTO THE CHANGING AGRICULTURAL CONTEXT)

I.1 Key emerging themes

Based on discussions in all five focus groups, several interrelated and important overarching themes emerged, providing insight into the perceptions, concerns, and hopes of young European farmers in today's evolving agricultural landscape, as shown in Graph 1 below and explained in the text.

Graph 1: Conceptual network of the nine emerging themes in discussions on changing agricultural context (Theme I)

The thematic network above is visualised as a conceptual graph, placing more strongly interconnected nine themes (represented as nine working codes) closer together while maintaining sufficient spacing between nodes for readability (see **APPENDIX 4**, particularly the final column).

Legend: 9 working codes stand for 9 emerging themes

- ECON-PRECARITY = Structural challenges and economic precarity*
- SUCCESSION = Generational transition and farm succession*
- LABOUR-SHORTAGE = Labour shortage and the crisis of workforce sustainability*
- CLIMATE-ADAPT = Climate change and environmental adaptation*
- DIGITAL-DIVIDE = Digitalization and technological disparities*
- GENDER-ROLE = Gender and the evolving role of women*
- POLICY-TRUST = Policy disillusionment and loss of trust*
- MENTAL HEALTH = Mental health and work-life balance*
- RESILIENCE-INNOV = Resilience and innovation amid uncertainty*

Structural challenges and economic precarity

A prevalent theme is the pervasive sense of economic instability faced by young farmers. Participants repeatedly emphasised the challenges posed by fluctuating market prices, burdensome bureaucratic requirements and insufficient share of profit margins compared to retailers and intermediaries. These conditions have created an atmosphere of economic precarity that discourages long-term investment and discourages new entrants from getting into farming, especially if there are high debts or land acquisition costs involved.

“The price of land is now completely unsustainable... It’s not really worth buying anymore.” (#6, IE)

“If you don’t come from a farming background ... it can be very difficult for young person to get into the industry because land prices are ridiculously high and it’s so hard to get started.” (#4, IE)

Frustration was particularly palpable among farmers from Poland and Slovenia, who pointed to the inconsistency of policies at EU level, including concerns about trade agreements such as MERCOSUR that jeopardise local production by competing with low-standard imports.

“We lack stability in the European Union’s agricultural policy... It’s the same as with beef from Argentina, Brazil and the USA. They can use growth hormones in their farming... we can’t compete with that.” (#13, PL)

In all groups, participants expressed great concern about the economic viability of agriculture. They cited low prices for products, high input costs and an unfair distribution of value along the supply chain. Competitive pressure in liberalised markets – particularly in relation to imports – exacerbates the precarious living situation of young farmers.

“You work a lot, but you realise that you can’t feed your family with all the work you do.” (#9, AT)

“Only about 40% of the milk prices on the shelves go back to the farmers... Everything is in between. And it’s getting less and less.” (#13, PL)

“We shouldn’t compete with the supermarkets... So, we would either have to get bigger or, as we have done, get into by-product production so we can set the price.” (#14, SI)

Generational transition and farm succession

There was a common concern in the focus groups about the feasibility of generational change. Many participants, particularly from France and Austria, spoke of uncertainties around succession, the burden of modernisation investment and the risks associated with long-term decisions that could be undermined by changing policy or market dynamics.

"If you choose one system, you have to continue with it because you are investing for 15 years or more... What will the political judgement be in 15 years? Climate change? War? We don't know." (#12, FR)

"Do we want to take over the farm? Do we want to start a life in agriculture? We both have a very good education. So we also have other job opportunities." (#1, AT)

The desire to continue farming is present in many, but is made more difficult by regulatory changes, climate adaptation requirements and income fluctuations.

"When you invest in farming, it's for 15 years or more... And what will happen in 15 years? We don't know ... Climate change [political crises, wars]?" (#12, FR)

"We work this way to have a chance and try not to be overwhelmed... We have 20 employees, so we also have to try to make sure that these 20 families ... can continue their lives through our farms." (#2, IT)

Labour shortage and the crisis of workforce sustainability

A persistent concern of young farmers in all countries was the growing difficulty of finding and retaining labour – both skilled and general. Labour shortages were described as a result of unattractive working conditions, low wages, generational turnover and the undervaluation of agricultural labour in society. In many contexts, participants emphasised that the future viability of farms depends not only on technology or markets, but also on who is actually doing the work.

"Many farmers are retiring ... Doing the crop is not a problem, but doing the milk – It's difficult to find a worker." (#12, FR)

"[Because of retirement] we have a lot of farms free now ... All the farms are getting bigger, but we try to keep our system simple so we can work with two or three people." (#11, FR)

"There is a shortage of labour, especially in the sectors where our farm is located ... I really hope that technology will come ... but we still need people ... and there is not enough co-operation between farmers." (#3, SI)

Labour concerns overlap strongly with the issue of generational change. When older farmers retire, their successors either do not enter the profession or are discouraged by unattractive conditions and regulatory requirements.

"The old farmers are dying and there are not enough young farmers coming in." (#10, EE)

In many cases, family members are overwhelmed, supplement the farm with part-time work or rely on outdated systems due to a lack of staff:

“In Austria, most farmers are part-time... farmers... So, this is a big burden for the families and also for the farmers themselves.” (#9, AT)

Labour shortages are thus both a symptom and a driver of deeper systemic stress: farms that cannot hire or pay workers are forced into cycles of intensification, consolidation or closure.

Climate change and environmental adaptation

Climate change was identified as a universal and urgent trend affecting all facets of agriculture. Farmers in all regions reported direct experience of changing weather patterns, shorter or unpredictable growing seasons and an increase in pests or diseases. There was also concern about increasing societal and regulatory pressure to mitigate environmental impacts without sufficient support or clarification from policy makers.

“Because of climate change, I believe I should change my farming activities. Switch more to livestock farming than crop farming... That way I can overcome the effects of climate change, which makes my calendar weirder.” (#7, UK)

“We have certain regulations ... for example, spreading slurry. But whenever you look out of the window, it’s like a summer’s day. And I think the farming calendar doesn’t really fit the current climate.” (#4, IE)

Farmers from Belgium and Estonia spoke about the contradictions in environmental policy, particularly in relation to grassland and animal husbandry, and the dissonance between environmental expectations and agricultural reality.

“If we want to preserve grassland [which stores the most carbon in the soil], we need cows or sheep or goats to utilise these lands. And they say ... we don’t want them, but you should keep the grassland. [So, what should we do]?” (#8, BE)

“We didn’t have snow until January... the winter wasn’t very winter... [It keeps changing]. You have to think, think, think ... and adapt.” (#10, EE)

Digitalization and technological disparities

The rise of digital technologies in agriculture was seen as both a necessary step forward and a point of tension. While younger farmers recognised the potential of precision farming and AI-based tools, several participants – particularly from Poland – pointed to the digital divide, citing the inadequate internet infrastructure in rural areas and the generational gap in digital literacy. In addition, many farmers expressed that the available scientific and technical knowledge does not reach the grassroots to a sufficient extent, leading to a discrepancy between policy objectives and practical implementation.

“European farmers are getting old... my parents are in their 60s and have problems with computers... I can’t imagine them using a drone... to do precision agriculture. ... And another

thing is that the internet in rural Poland is just terrible, that's one of the biggest problems." (#17, PL)

"Everything has changed... now it's about ... Robots, drones ... Big Data ... The farmers who ... can utilise some new technologies to reduce costs are the winners." (#10, EE)

"Eventually I'd like to develop software that allows you to track any livestock on the farm and use it on your phone." (#7, UK)

Gender and the evolving role of women

Women farmers, particularly in the focus group (FG1), which consisted entirely of women, emphasised their unique contributions and challenges in the agricultural sector. Participants noted that women-led farms often pursue more diversified and socially orientated business models, such as educational farms or farms that support social care initiatives. However, there are still barriers, particularly in terms of access to capital and being recognised as equal decision-makers.

"A female perspective always brings different thoughts to the sector ... and sometimes different business models ... like working with disabled people or setting up schools on farms. This is something that is mostly implemented by women." (#1, AT)

"It is very important that women farmers work on a farm and have the same role as everyone else ... not just as a farmer's wife or as someone who works, but also as someone who has the responsibility." (#3, SI)

"Our sensitivity to food, to the whole value chain in agriculture is something important... as a woman, it's about something more." (#2, IT).

Policy disillusionment and loss of trust

The feeling of being disconnected from political decision-making processes was omnipresent. Many young farmers expressed the feeling that policy is being made without adequate consultation or understanding of the realities on the ground. The lack of a stable, coherent agricultural policy at both national and EU level was frequently cited as a major obstacle to planning and optimism for the future.

"We used to have the Green Deal and Farm to Fork... then came the Strategic Dialogue ... and yesterday Christophe Hansen published something new. ... One of the biggest problems is that not even the policy is stable." (#17, PL)

"What is also missing a bit is a clear political perspective ... what do we expect from farming in 30 years. ... Many farmers are afraid that primary production will be shifted to other countries ... It's not clear what the priority is [price, sustainability or production]." (#1, AT)

"You have 2, 5, 10% of CAP funds less [if you miss something] ... And it's really stressful because you should know everything about everything." (#8, BE)

Mental health and work-life balance

Although this did not come up in all groups, where it did (particularly in FG3), participants mentioned the psychological toll of farming. Young farmers reported burnout, feelings of isolation and pressure from societal expectations and policy requirements. Those who run a farm alongside another job reported a relentless workload and little room for rest or leisure.

"You have two jobs... working in the barn, in the field and another job... And then there's the pressure from society as a whole... politics... They want more and more, and we just can't do it anymore." (#9, AT)

Resilience and innovation amid uncertainty

Despite these challenges, a counter-theme of resilience and innovation emerged. Farmers talked about strategies such as diversification, direct sales to consumers and the development of niche products as ways to maintain their autonomy and secure their income. However, this entrepreneurial spirit was often presented as a necessity rather than a choice - a means to survive rather than thrive.

"We have our own customers; we don't sell to the slaughterhouse... We make our own prices. But if new regulations shut us down, we will have to rethink everything." (#15, SI)

"Diversifying exploration is the key to success... If I have cherries and it's a bad year, I can compensate with vineyards..." (#5, PT)

"I want to develop software that allows you to track any livestock on the farm and use it on your mobile phone. At some point I can sell the idea to someone." (#7, UK)

I.2 Pressures and stresses

The narratives of young European farmers reveal a complex web of economic, environmental and emotional challenges embedded in the broader neoliberal and politicised context of contemporary agriculture.

Economic precarity and unstable markets form the basis of much of their distress. Young farmers consistently described an exploitative economic environment characterised by unstable income streams, diminishing market power and great vulnerability to global economic forces. Many are forced to juggle multiple jobs just to survive, with the high cost of living and barriers to housing adding to their insecurity. These findings underline the pressures resulting from a neoliberal market logic characterised by supermarket monopolies, global competition and retreating public safety nets.

Bureaucratic overload and political instability represent an additional burden. Farmers often described the administrative and regulatory landscape as punitive and unstable. Even minor bureaucratic delays can lead to significant financial consequences, as one participant noted. Others spoke of the challenge of committing to long-term infrastructure in the face of changing political priorities. Contradictory policies – such as the requirement to switch to cage-free systems without the necessary permitting support – are an example of the contradictions within the EU agricultural framework, where innovation is simultaneously encouraged and hindered.

Climate change and environmental stressors have evolved from abstract problems to immediate, destabilising forces in daily farming practice. The unpredictability of seasonal patterns, even in regions historically accustomed to climatic extremes, is now disrupting planning and production cycles. From Estonia to Ireland, farmers are facing unprecedented weather anomalies that jeopardise feed, mobility and livestock health. The feeling that nature itself has become unreliable is adding to the emotional strain of farming.

Finally, the problems of workload, social exclusion and mental health run through all dimensions of their experience. Many young farmers work isolated and physically demanding jobs, while maintaining off-farm employment. The pressure to fulfil both agricultural and societal expectations leads to exhaustion, frustration and emotional burnout. While mental health issues were not always explicitly addressed, they regularly surfaced an indication of a silent crisis brewing beneath the surface of European rural life.

I.3 Hopes

Amidst the complex pressures faced by young European farmers, a counter-narrative emerges, based on innovation, reimagined values and adaptation strategies. The participants' statements reflect a dynamic reorientation of agricultural life towards resilience, autonomy and inclusivity.

Diversification as resilience stands out as a key strategy for coping with economic and environmental volatility. Participants described diversification not only as a reactive measure, but as a proactive framework to mitigate risks, make farming both economically viable and attractive to younger generations, or to stabilise income.

Localism and consumer education also emerged as a central theme, based on the vision of reconnecting agriculture with the local economy and ethical consumption. Rather than competing directly with globalised agribusiness, farmers are committed to quality, regionality and community.

The feminisation of farming and inclusive leadership signal a broader cultural shift within the sector. Female participants advocated for more holistic, socially engaged and educational farming models. These perspectives indicate not only a shift in gender roles, but also a profound redefinition of what constitutes legitimate agricultural knowledge, leadership and practice.

Finally, technological possibilities – if democratised presents a vision of cautious optimism. Although technology can cause anxiety, especially when it appears to threaten human roles, many participants emphasised its potential – when it is equally accessible and contextually integrated. All contributions welcomed technology as a complement to human labour – not a replacement – offering more control and adaptability without displacing the central role of the farmer.

I.4 Conclusion

In the **changing landscape of European agriculture**, young farmers articulate a deeply ambivalent understanding of their present and future. Their narratives reflect an awareness of **structural fragility** – from economic precarity and labour shortages to climatic disruption and political inconsistency. This context fosters a sense of vulnerability that discourages long-term engagement, generational change and sustainable innovation. The **weight of uncertainty** – economic, political and environmental – has become a defining feature of farming life, and many describe a profession characterised more by survival than well-being.

At the same time, young farmers are not passive recipients of the crisis. Their reflections reveal an emerging **ethos of adaptive resilience**, in which diversification, localism, inclusive leadership and careful use of technology are mobilised as tools of resistance and renewal. Through strategic innovation and community engagement, these young farmers are resisting the constraints of a neoliberal and politically fragmented system. They are trying to reclaim agency over their livelihoods and redefine agriculture on their own terms.

To summarise, today's young European farmers are engaged in a profession that is suspended between **precariousness and opportunity**. They are under pressure from the system, but at the same time they are inspired by a vision of farming that is **more diverse**, more **localised** and more **socially rooted** than the models they have inherited.

THEME II (GENERATIONAL CHANGE)

II.1 Key emerging themes

Based on the five focus group discussions, several key themes emerged regarding the conditions for successful generational change in agriculture, reflecting both structural challenges and cultural dynamics in different countries and farm types, as shown in Graph 2 below.

Graph 2: Conceptual network of the seven emerging themes in discussions on generational change (Theme II)

The thematic network above is visualised as a conceptual graph, placing more strongly interconnected seven themes (represented as seven working codes) closer together while maintaining sufficient spacing between nodes for readability (see APPENDIX 4, particularly the final column).

Legend: 7 working codes stand for 7 emerging themes

- TRAD-INNOV = Tension Between Tradition and Innovation*
- STRUCT = Structural Inequities and Gatekeeping*
- EMOTIONS = Emotional Labour and Psychological Readiness*
- IMAGINARY = The Social Imaginary of Farming*
- UNCERTAINTY = The Uncertainty of the Future*
- LEARNING = Learning and Knowledge Flows*
- ASPIRATIONS = Aspirational Models for the Future Farm*

Tension between tradition and innovation

A strong and recurring theme was the negotiation between preserving legacy and fostering innovation. In all focus groups, participants expressed a desire to respect the values and practices of previous generations while introducing technological, ecological and organisational change and demanding the freedom to modernise. This often leads to conflict with older generations who resist change or present structural barriers to change (e.g. entrenched land use patterns). To illustrate:

“You couldn’t say to the younger generation, okay, yeah, you’re the farm manager, but you do what I tell you to do.” (#10, EE)

“When I took over the farm, my father gave me a free hands... Nowadays he says, ‘I don’t know what you’re doing.’” (#10, EE)

“The next generation should still change things, but also respect their elders for their work.” (#9, AT)

This theme reflects a universal negotiation between continuity and change in farm succession.

Structural inequities and gatekeeping

In several discussions it became clear that access to land, capital and knowledge continues to be unequally distributed – both according to socio-economic status and gender.

Land markets are described as inflated and speculative, especially in countries such as Poland and Italy, which excludes newcomers.

Bureaucratic hurdles and policy design often favour established (mostly male, family-run) farmers. Participants from all countries were very frustrated by the unequal distribution of land, credit and policy benefits – particularly to the detriment of newcomers and women. To illustrate:

“[Because of CAP payments or projects] they [young farmers] give their names... but who is really farming is their parents, their grandparents. ... In the statistics, you are not a young farmer, you are just a person that is young farming... But in terms of CAP direct payments, if you apply for those funds but you don’t have a project, you are receiving the same as an old person.” (#5, PT).

“If you don’t have experience at the start, you can make decisions that lead to bankruptcy.” (#13, PL)

“[Credit institutions] always want the parents to give a guarantee for the loan.” (#2, IT)

Such mechanisms perpetuate intergenerational privileges and dependencies and make it difficult for new entrants to enter the sector.

Women also reported institutional blind spots - from education tracking to maternity policies - that subtly perpetuate marginalisation.

Across all groups, these structural barriers reinforce the perception that agriculture is closed to outsiders, reducing its attractiveness to urban youth or people from non-farming backgrounds.

Emotional labour and psychological readiness

The participants recognised that emotional resilience and support are just as important as technical and economic preparation.

Succession is not only a legal or financial act, but also a relational and identity-related process that is often complicated by silence, guilt or misunderstandings between generations.

In addition to the physical and financial preparation, succession also involves an emotional complexity that is often overlooked or stigmatised. Farmers expressed a desire for counselling and psychological services: "It's a bit of a stigma if you have problems and no one wants to talk to others about their problems, but I think that would be very important." (#9, AT)

Mental health concerns were subtly expressed through references to exhaustion, lack of days off and loneliness. This theme cuts across all nationalities, genders and even levels of farming modernisation, suggesting that emotional challenges are embedded in farmers' lives.

The social imaginary of farming

Participants from different contexts described how public perception influences identity, pride and recruitment in agriculture. The profession is often portrayed as underappreciated, "old-fashioned" or media-depicted as crisis-ridden (e.g. "The news is always about problems in farming" – #11, FR). At the same time, many are trying to reclaim the topic via social media, community events or school programmes to present farming as "sexy again" (#10, EE), meaningful and modern.

"We take children from primary school ... to the farm, show them a farm and show them exactly what happens there. And many of them were quite amazed that so much happens in farming that they had absolutely no idea about." (#6, IE)

Participants questioned the stigma and emphasised pride in the profession.

The uncertainty of the future

Climate change, volatile markets and political changes are causing problems for young farmers. This existential uncertainty overlaps with every other issue. Despite all their passion, many young farmers are uncertain about their future.

"The way things are going I was wondering if there is a future for me in agriculture." (#6, IE)

Several participants explicitly questioned whether they would stay in farming at all, citing stress and instability as reasons. The theme also highlights differences: larger or better supported farms are better able to plan, while smallholders express fear of collapse or

stagnation. This highlights a difference in resilience, where some farmers are buffered by structural support, while others remain vulnerable to systemic shocks.

"If there are farms that have had no investment in the last 30, 40 or 50 years, and you take over that farm ... then you have nothing. And there is ... a lot of investment that you have to make." (#9, AT)

"You don't want to impose these hardships on your children to get out of this financial hole." (#10, EE)

This theme runs through all regions and reflects a collective vulnerability and need for stability.

Finally, some of them emphasised adaptability and freedom as core values: "The next generation has to do what they want. ... So, on my farm, I don't build anything that can't be changed." (#12, FR).

Learning and knowledge flows

The educational divide – between theory and practice, old and young, formal and informal learning – runs through all groups. The call for practical, land-based education shows the frustration with the limitations of traditional schooling and the discrepancy between formal education and actual needs.

"If someone goes to university, comes back and wants to start a farm... they know nothing. And they are immediately confronted with bureaucracy." (#13, PL)

"Agriculture courses should take place on the land... not just in theory." (#5, PT)

At the same time, many acknowledge that learning also takes place informally through the family or community, although this is not always accessible to newcomers.

The gender and rural-urban divide in educational pathways - "It's still called boys' school" (#9, AT) – points to a socialisation gap that starts early.

This theme runs through all age, gender and geographical strata, emphasising the idea that knowledge transfer is as much a cultural as an educational issue.

Aspirational models for the future farm

Despite the obstacles, participants expressed hope and determination about the farms they would like to build or pass on. As mentioned earlier (see Table 8: Ideal farm to pass on), common aspirations included economic viability, technological modernisation, environmental and well-being sustainability, and work-life balance.

However, these aspirations are always shaped by contextual constraints: In mountainous regions, for example, even owning 100 cows is a goal (#13, PL), while in other regions the focus is more on diversification or innovation.

In all groups, participants expressed the hope of building farms that are personally meaningful to them – a balance between tradition and change. This theme emphasises that farming is a living project and not a static legacy — a project shaped by values, choices and an evolving future.

II.2 Pressures and stresses

Young farmers across Europe are under increasing pressure as they transition into farming, pressures that are closely intertwined with the complexities of generational change. At the centre of this pressure is a deep sense of structural insecurity and economic anxiety. Many young entrants inherit undercapitalised farms that are burdened with debt and outdated infrastructure and have limited access to land, credit or adequate institutional support. The expectation to have immediate technical expertise and strategic vision adds to this pressure and highlights the critical mismatch between the demands placed on new farmers and the resources available to them. For those entering without a farming background, the barriers are even higher. The bureaucratic complexity of agricultural subsidies, such as the CAP, exacerbates this strain and makes the support mechanisms a source of constant stress.

Added to this are the generational conflicts associated with many succession processes. Even when a formal handover occurs, younger farmers often report a lack of real authority or autonomy, while older generations continue to exercise control over key decisions. This dynamic often inhibits innovation and delays the necessary adaptation to changing market or environmental conditions. In addition, successors often inherit the consequences of years of underinvestment— - materially, strategically and emotionally — without being given the freedom to chart a new course.

These tensions are exacerbated by mental health vulnerabilities and a culture of silence that pervades rural life. Emotional distress, chronic overwork and social isolation are widespread, particularly in sectors such as dairy farming where labour is constant. Mental health remains highly stigmatised and there are few support structures tailored to the particular stresses faced by young farmers. For women, these stresses are further intensified by gender-specific barriers, ranging from inadequate maternity support to systemic biases in training and public perception, reinforcing their marginalisation within the farming profession.

Bureaucracy also proves to be a source of institutional mistrust. Many express disappointments with regulatory systems that are punitive rather than supportive. Compliance controls, disease control measures and subsidy mechanisms are often described as inflexible and disconnected from the reality on the ground, contributing to a widespread sense of vulnerability and institutional alienation.

Finally, these social and cultural pressures are exacerbated by a lack of recognition and isolation. Young farmers complain of a growing disconnect between agricultural labour and

public perception, noting a lack of respect and understanding for their work. Media reports that focus on the crisis rather than resilience reinforce this sense of cultural marginalisation and make it more difficult to attract successors or cultivate pride in the profession.

To summarise, the pressures of generational change are not limited to succession logistics — they are embedded in broader structures of economic instability, gender inequality, bureaucratic dysfunction and cultural misrecognition. Without targeted and empathetic intervention, these interlocking pressures risk undermining the sustainability of farming for the next generation.

II.3 Hopes

Young farmers' hopes for generational change are not limited to the logistical transfer of assets or land – they are rooted in a transformative vision of what agriculture should become: viable, inclusive, forward-looking and people-centred. These aspirations reveal a desire to not only preserve farming as it is, but to reimagine it as a profession that fosters innovation, well-being and social respect.

At the centre of these aspirations is the ambition for a viable and modern heritage. Young farmers want to inherit farms that are financially stable, structurally sound and equipped with the necessary tools and technology to survive in today's competitive and climate uncertain environment. Their goal is not just continuity, but progress — they want to inherit farms that are ready for innovation and not burdened by the shortcomings of previous generations. Modernisation, particularly through digital tools and automation, is seen as essential for resilience and relevance.

Equally central is the call for dialogue between generations and mutual respect. Participants expressed a clear desire for cross-generational collaboration rather than top-down inheritance. They would like to be involved in decision-making processes at an early stage and be recognised not as assistants but as partners in shaping the farm's future. This desire speaks in favour of a change from hierarchical to relational succession models, in which empowerment and co-creation take the place of obedience and control.

Furthermore, young farmers envision an autonomous and flexible succession in which the next generation has the freedom to adapt the business to their own values, goals and abilities. Instead of being tied to rigid inheritances, they are looking for adaptable frameworks that allow for creativity, individual identity and innovation. This perspective redefines legacy as a living process, shaped by dialogue, agency and responsiveness rather than static replication.

Beyond the internal structure of succession, young farmers are also calling for renewal through recognition and inclusion. They hope for a cultural and institutional environment that recognises farming as a respected and indispensable profession. This includes breaking down gender barriers, promoting public appreciation of agricultural work and ensuring that young farmers – regardless of their background – receive the support they need to build a meaningful future in agriculture.

Finally, their aspirations culminate in a vision for sustainable, people-centred farms. These are places where ecological responsibility, emotional well-being and intergenerational solidarity go hand in hand with economic success. The ideal farm, in their view, is not only profitable, but also healthy, humane and safe – a place where successors can thrive without inheriting the burdens of burnout, isolation or precarity.

In short, young farmers' hopes see the generational transition not as a handover of responsibility, but as a transformative opportunity to renew the agricultural sector with new values, inclusive practices and a vision of sustainability that is both personal and global.

II.4 Conclusion

The process of **generational change** in European agriculture is turning out to be a profound process of transformation – a crossroads where the future of farming is both **challenged and reimagined**. As the voices of young farmers show, succession is not just an economic or administrative event, but a complex negotiation of **identity, values, power and opportunity**.

On one side is a matrix of **structural and cultural pressures**: intergenerational tensions, gender inequalities, emotional and psychological stresses, and systemic barriers to access to land, capital and institutional support. These pressures often place young farmers in positions of **responsibility without agency**. They are expected to uphold traditions while lacking the authority or resources to innovate. Emotional readiness and relationship stress are often overlooked dimensions of succession, exacerbated by a culture of silence and societal misrecognition.

Yet within this web of constraints, there is also a strong counter-current of **aspiration and vision**. Young farmers are not just inheriting farms – they are trying **to redefine what farming can be**. Their hopes are for **dialogue-based succession**, modernisation of infrastructure and digitalisation, and inclusive systems that promote autonomy, well-being and social recognition. They envision farms that are not only economically viable, but also **ecologically responsible and emotionally sustainable**.

Finally, these young farmers see generational change as a **political and cultural opportunity** to reshape the future of farming: from hierarchical to collaborative, from extractive to regenerative, and from isolating to rooted in community. Without meaningful intervention to address the embedded structural barriers, these aspirations risk being undermined. If supported, however, they have the potential to **revitalise European agriculture**.

THEME III (CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES TO IMPROVE WORKING ENVIRONMENT)

III.1 Key emerging themes

Based on a thematic analysis of the discussions in the five focus groups, several prominent cross-cutting themes emerge that summarise the common experiences, anticipations, and structural challenges that shape the working conditions and future expectations of European farmers, as shown in Graph 3 below.

Graph 3: Conceptual network of the six emerging themes in discussions on improving the working environment (Theme III)

The thematic network above is visualised as a conceptual graph, placing more strongly interconnected six themes (represented as six working codes) closer together while maintaining sufficient spacing between nodes for readability (see **APPENDIX 4**, particularly the final column).

Legend: 6 working codes stand for 6 emerging themes

- WLB = Work-Life Balance & Mental Health*
- GENDER = Gender, Family Dynamics & Invisible Labour*
- TECH = Technological Modernisation & Ambivalences*
- LABOUR = Labour Shortage & Succession Crisis*
- SOCIAL PERC = Social Perception, Bureaucracy & Moral Pressure*
- ECON = Economic Fragility & Uncertainty*

The central importance of work-life balance and mental health

The difficulty of achieving a sustainable work-life balance in agriculture was emphasised in all focus groups, as #17 (PL) clearly expressed:

“There is no work-life balance in agriculture. I work from March to November, all day long, and then I'm almost on holiday for the remaining three or even four months. It drives me crazy when I have nothing to do.”

Participants emphasised the mixing of home and work life, which is exacerbated by round-the-clock farming duties, the lack of structured holidays and limited access to external support (e.g. through a work replacement service). This is particularly true for mothers and caregivers, such as participants #1 (AT) and #14 (SI), who have to manage both domestic responsibilities and physically demanding work.

In addition, concerns about mental health – including stress, loneliness and anxiety – were repeatedly expressed. Participant #10 (EE) aptly described today's farming (working conditions) as “mental gymnastics” that requires sustained cognitive and emotional engagement beyond the physical labour. Farmers also commented that they felt mentally overwhelmed due to financial insecurity, lack of social interaction and societal misperceptions. To illustrate:

“I think it's very difficult when you're on the farm all the time and have no other structure or routine to stay mentally happy and in a good place.” (#4, IE)

Gender, family dynamics and invisible labour

The gendered division of labour and the invisibility of women's contributions came up in several groups. Participants emphasised the complications associated with maternity leave, the lack of structural support for caregiving and the underestimated psychological burden that women carry on farms. The idea of family cooperation emerged as both a strength and a stress factor. Participants repeatedly highlighted the difficulty of working with family members on a daily basis without professional or emotional boundaries and emphasised the need for better communication and social security for unpaid family workers. To illustrate:

“In farming, you can't just close the office for a year. So, you can't really take a break and go on maternity leave. ... It's not that easy to find someone to do the work within a day.... That's why most of the people who replace the working people on the farm are family members who know the farm very well.” (#1, AT)

“It's really a challenge to be with the same people all day ... We are not very good at communicating in this farming sector.” (#3, SI)

Technological modernisation and its ambivalences

There is cautious optimism that digitalisation and automation could improve working conditions or compensate for labour shortages in agriculture. Farmers have recognised that

technological advances - milking robots, drones, AI systems - can alleviate physical strain and labour shortages. However, participants also expressed concerns about over-reliance on technology, barriers to access and investment costs. For example, #17 (PL) expressed scepticism about the reliability of AI and raised questions about misinformation from automated systems such as ChatGPT, drawing a line between technological assistance and professional knowledge.

Another major concern is training and education. Many participants argued that the successful adoption of technology depends on continuous learning and the collective sharing of knowledge. Participant #2 (IT) emphasised the need for farmers to "keep up to date" and for associations to facilitate peer-to-peer learning.

Labour shortage and the crisis of successors

A striking theme in all groups was the lack of qualified and willing agricultural labour. The seasonal labour force is getting older and younger generations are reluctant to participate in physically intensive agricultural work. As participant #3 (SI) stated, even finding seasonal labour in Slovenia is difficult due to language barriers and decreasing interest.

This is directly related to a broader succession crisis. Several participants emphasised the lack of attractiveness of farming for young people, citing economic instability, high investment requirements and societal devaluation. Participant #2 (IT) lamented that many young people have "lost the knowledge" and desire to return to the land, suggesting the need for a cultural reevaluation of farming.

"It's hard to find someone who really wants to help you ... Young people don't want hard labour. They want a good job ... If we can't find them [workers], we have to reduce our labour. And that's not fair. ... So, yes, like I said, try to improve people's knowledge about what our labour means." (#2, IT)

Social perception, bureaucracy and moral pressure

Another cross-cutting theme is the influence of public and societal perception on the morality and identity of farmers. Several participants, especially in Austria and Slovenia, mentioned an increasing hostility towards certain types of farms - e.g. pig farming - in the context of animal welfare activism. Participant #9 (AT) described how children from pig farming families are bullied at school, indicating a high emotional toll on farm households.

This theme also includes frustration with bureaucratic and political control. Participants #11 (FR) and #12 (FR) noted that despite the positive intentions behind policy oversight (e.g., environmental regulations), the constant checks and administrative requirements add stress, often leaving farmers feeling distrusted and undervalued.

"Sometimes you hear too many political directives in one year. ... A lot of people ... spend a lot of time looking after us. Sometimes you just want to say, 'Stop. We're not doing bad things.'" (#11, FR)

Economic fragility and structural uncertainty

Finally, the financial fragility of farming was repeatedly emphasised. From discussions of low incomes and limited investment to dependence on Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) subsidies, farmers in all contexts expressed concern about economic sustainability. Participant #8 (BE) noted that without a “strong CAP” many farms could not survive and that a better income would make farmers' work less dangerous, while participant #9 (AT) warned that modernisation would exacerbate inequalities if not accompanied by solid public support.

III.2 Pressures and stresses

The working conditions of young European farmers are shaped by a complex web of physical, emotional, economic and societal pressures that are deeply embedded in the structure and culture of agricultural life. These pressures are not just occupational — they shape farmers’ identities, well-being and visions for the future.

A central and recurring theme is the work-life imbalance, with farming described as a profession in which the boundary between private and professional life is largely non-existent. The daily routine is dictated by the rhythm of the animals and the seasons, leaving little room for rest, holidays or maternity and sick leave. This chronic lack of time leads to emotional exhaustion and disrupts family life, particularly for women who often carry the invisible burden of caring and unpaid labour — roles that are structurally unsupported and socially undervalued.

These conditions lead to an endemic mental health crisis. Participants spoke of ongoing stress, emotional isolation and burnout, exacerbated by generational responsibilities, societal expectations and a lack of psychological support. Cultural norms in agriculture often discourage emotional vulnerability, leading to a silent crisis that influences decisions related to succession, safety, and innovation. The perception of stress as “normal” only reinforces the lack of visibility and response to this critical issue.

Labour challenges add another layer of vulnerability. The sector faces an invisible crisis of replacement, with a declining pool of skilled and willing workers. Family labour—often unpaid and ageing—fills the gap, but the long-term sustainability of this model is increasingly questioned. An intergenerational knowledge gap is emerging as younger people are discouraged by the physical demands and low status of farm work, while external labour remains difficult to attract due to wage constraints and social barriers.

While technological change is promising, it also brings its own fears. Automation and artificial intelligence are seen as necessary to reduce labour and adapt to environmental regulations, but also require capital investment, new skills and mental adaptability. Many farmers feel caught between the promise of innovation and the mental strain of keeping up with rapid digital change under public scrutiny.

Societal pressure and false recognition add to the work stress. Negative media portrayals, activist-led inspections, and consumer hypocrisy (e.g. demanding organic standards while accepting food waste) contribute to a growing sense of public hostility. In some cases, this has led to shame and stigmatisation. Farmers' children hide their family profession because they are bullied, reflecting a wider cultural divide between producers and society.

Finally, economic insecurity and political volatility underlie almost all of these stressors. Insecure incomes, over-reliance on off-farm employment, and delayed infrastructure improvements are the result of a system that lacks financial stability. The bureaucratic overload of agricultural policy – particularly the CAP – has been widely described as an obstacle to safety, efficiency and long-term planning. Without adequate support, farmers must manage risk in a system that does little to mitigate structural uncertainty.

Taken together, the working conditions of young farmers reflect a profession that is under great systemic pressure - labour that is not only physically demanding, but also emotionally taxing, economically unstable and socially devalued. These interwoven pressures reveal an urgent need for holistic, empathetic and inclusive reforms that address both the visible and invisible dimensions of agricultural labour.

III.3 Hopes

Young European farmers articulate a clear and collective vision for changing working conditions in agriculture. Their aspirations reveal an urgent desire to move away from the traditional models of ruthless labour and towards a profession that is liveable, humane and future-oriented.

At the heart of this vision is a belief in automation and digital innovation as catalysts for labour relief. Technological tools such as milking robots, biogas plants and digital monitoring are seen as essential not only for improving productivity, but also for reorganising the rhythm of life on the farm. These tools offer the possibility of temporal autonomy and help farmers reclaim rest, flexibility and mental clarity. This shift also reflects the evolution of farmers into knowledge-based managers – hybrid professionals who operate in both manual and digital domains, often within networks where they learn together.

In addition to technological change, farmers express a deep longing for work-life balance and regularity of time. The longing for holidays, predictable routines or simply moments to get away from the constant demands can be found across all regions and sectors. This desire reflects a broader rejection of traditional expectations that equate value with exhaustion. Instead, young farmers want a future in which farming is compatible with a fulfilling human life, not in opposition to it.

Linked to these hopes is the dream of economic stability. The participants plead for fairer market systems, better support from the CAP and greater recognition of agricultural value by consumers. Financial security is not desired as a means to wealth, but as a basis for safer, healthier and more independent work. The ability to invest in infrastructure or afford labour is seen as essential for physical and mental safety.

Many also emphasise community-based solutions to individual vulnerability. From co-operative maternity leave to peer learning networks, young farmers envision a future based on collectivism rather than isolation. This points to a redefinition of resilience – not as individual resilience, but as mutual care and institutional solidarity.

These visions also contain a strong intergenerational message. Rather than romanticising farm succession, participants call for modernisation and safety as prerequisites for youth engagement. The hope is that the next generation will not inherit the stress and hardship of farming, but its purpose, autonomy and social value. With this forward-looking identity, life in the countryside is portrayed as desirable rather than arduous.

Finally, underlying all other hopes is the aspiration for mental well-being. The desire for rest, self-care and emotional support shows a keen awareness of the psychological toll that farming takes. But even more than services, farmers are striving for a cultural change – for a reorientation of farming as a profession where people are at the centre and caring for the land includes caring for one's own body.

To summarise, young farmers are not simply seeking better working conditions – they envision a different way of being a farmer, where technology, community and dignity come together to support a life that is sustainable in every way: physically, emotionally, economically and socially.

III.4 Conclusion

The working conditions of young European farmers, as revealed through cross-national focus group discussions, illustrate a profession that is struggling with **deep systemic problems**, and yet is inspired by a collective vision for change. Currently, everyday life in agriculture is characterised by **relentless labour intensity, emotional exhaustion, gender inequalities, economic vulnerability** and **societal misrecognition**. The traditional rhythm of agricultural life, shaped by seasonal demands, intergenerational dependencies and bureaucratic pressure, often renders the boundaries between work and rest obsolete. This is particularly stressful for women, who take on invisible, unpaid and often unsupported caring and farming tasks.

Mental health issues stemming from overwork, loneliness and the cultural stigmatisation of vulnerability cut across national and sectoral lines, revealing a silent crisis at the core of agricultural labour. At the same time, the profession is undergoing demographic and labour shift, with a **lack of successors** and **dwindling labour force participation** posing an existential challenge. While **technological modernisation** offers hope, it also leads to new pressures in terms of skills, investment and adaptation under public scrutiny.

Amidst these challenges, however, young farmers articulate a hopeful and pragmatic vision: a future where **technology eases physical strain**, work-life balance is no longer a luxury, and **community-based models of care and resilience replace individualised stress**. They envision a profession in which **dignity, autonomy and mental well-being** are of

fundamental importance and in which **economic profitability** is once again **combined with social respect and intergenerational continuity**.

Finally, the discourse on working conditions is not just about professional reform – it reflects a deep desire to **redefine the culture of farming itself**. Young farmers want not just better tools and policies, but a **new social contract**: one in which farming is recognised as a worthwhile, purposeful and respected way of life, based on care for the land and the people who farm it.

THEME IV (POLICY NEEDS)

IV.1 Key emerging themes

Several overarching themes also emerged regarding the policy needs of young farmers within the current and future EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and national frameworks. These narratives, drawn from different national contexts and gender perspectives, reflect common concerns as well as contextual nuances, as illustrated below and shown in Graph 4.

Graph 4: Conceptual network of the eight emerging themes in discussions on policy needs (Theme IV)

The thematic network above is visualised as a conceptual graph, placing more strongly interconnected eight themes (represented as eight working codes) closer together while

maintaining sufficient spacing between nodes for readability (see **APPENDIX 4**, particularly the final column).

Legend: 8 working codes stand for 8 emerging themes

ENTRY-BARRIERS = Structural & Financial Barriers to Entry and Generational Renewal

MARKET-STABILITY = Uncertain Markets & Need for Economic Stability

CAP-SIMPLIFY = Clearer, Simpler & Better-Targeted CAP

SOCIAL-RIGHTS = Social Infrastructure, Work-Life Balance & Support Services

ECO-COMPENSATION = Ecological Frustration & Under-Compensation

RURAL-INFRA = Territorial Cohesion & Rural Infrastructure

FARM-IMAGE = Cultural Recognition & Public Perception of Farming

TRADE-STANDARDS = Trade & Standards: MERCOSUR Criticism and 'European Quality Food'

Structural and financial barriers to entry and generational renewal

In almost all focus groups, participants emphasised the difficulties that young people face when entering the agricultural sector. These included access to land, high start-up costs, succession problems and insufficient financial support in the initial phase. For example, participants #1 (AT) and #6 (IE) called for stronger succession regulations and support for newly established farmers and referred to promising practices in France and Austria.

Several participants pointed out that it is difficult to secure land and capital before a viable farm can be established. Participant #10 (EE) emphasised the importance of initial capital subsidies (e.g. €100,000 start-up aid in Estonia), while participant #12 (FR) raised concerns about dependence on subsidies and the resulting systemic vulnerability: "It is also difficult to go to the bank and ask for a million euros to buy a farm and start farming. ... So politicians have to help with money, advice and guidance." #12 (FR)

Uncertain markets and need for economic stability

Young farmers emphasised the priority of stable markets and fair prices over dependence on subsidies. Participant #13 (PL), for example, emphasised that economic predictability takes precedence over ecological and social investments: "Everything is based on money... A stable market is more important because someone who works hard will see the fruits of their labour."

In this context, subsidies were not seen as a sufficient substitute, but as part of a larger economic architecture that needs to be reformed, including better pricing mechanisms and market support for local and sustainable production, as discussed by participant #14 (SI) and #8 (BE).

Clearer, simpler and better-targeted CAP

A recurring and urgent theme was the overwhelming bureaucracy associated with the CAP and national agricultural programmes. Participant #3 (SI) expressed his deep frustration with the complex application procedures, the opacity of the policy and the administrative overload that discourages many small farmers and young entrants: "Agricultural policy

should be clearer for us farmers... we do all the bureaucracy, all the taxes, all the reporting ourselves.”

Participant #9 (AT) called for a simplification of CAP regulations, claiming that the current framework discourages participation and fragments young people's interest in farming. Instead, she favours “a certain framework across Europe to incentivise young farmers, investment and ... labour force.”

Social infrastructure, work-life balance and support services

Social policies – particularly maternity leave, healthcare, mental health support and replacement services – were discussed at length, especially in the women's and mixed-gender groups. Austria stood out in particular: #1 (AT) and #9 (AT) praised existing structures such as maternity leave for women farmers, pension parity and accident assistance in agriculture.

Participants from Slovenia, Poland and Ireland, on the other hand, pointed to deficits in access to childcare, mental health care and representation of women's labour. Participant #4 (IE) highlighted gendered invisibility in pension entitlements and called for policy reforms that recognise unpaid work in agriculture: “You've done your whole working life and the only person entitled [to a pension] is the husband.... It's just so unfair.”

Ecological frustration and under-compensation

There is a considerable tension between the demands of environmental protection and the inadequate remuneration for ecological services. Farmers such as #3 (SI) explicitly expressed dissatisfaction with eco-schemes that only cover part of the costs, especially in protected areas (e.g. Natura 2000) where obligations are high but compensation is minimal or non-existent: “Now we have a lot of things to do and we don't get paid for them. When we are on the market, we are just like everyone else.”

Similarly, #7 (UK) called for the phasing out of industrial fertilisation and the revival of soil health, as the environment is central to the long-term viability of farming.

Territorial cohesion and rural infrastructure

Echoing the EU's objectives, the need for balanced territorial development was emphasised by #5 (PT), who stressed that remoteness from markets, lack of rural services and deficits in healthcare structurally marginalise young farmers: “In my case, I am really far away from the markets and the people who can consume our products. For me, the CAP is the key to the success of farming and also of young farmers when it comes to developing the cohesion of the whole country and the whole EU.”

Rural revitalisation, access to education and support for digitalisation were also highlighted, especially by participants such as #17 (PL) and #14 (SI), who advocated for equal educational

opportunities in the countryside, including language learning and flexible learning systems for farming families.

Cultural recognition and public perception of farming

Participants felt that farming is misunderstood, undervalued and increasingly isolated from society. Participants #10 (EE) and #11 (FR) called for public communication campaigns and food literacy, especially among urban populations. The social role of farmers needs to be re-legitimised through actions that promote generational pride, community support and school-farm collaboration.

“There should be some marketing ... showing how food is produced. That's something we should definitely promote.” (#10, EE)

Trade and standards: MERCOSUR criticism and ‘European quality food’

Several farmers, in particular #11 (FR), voiced frustrated and morally charged criticism of trade agreements such as MERCOSUR, pointing to contradictions between EU sustainability rhetoric and free trade practices that undermine domestic agriculture: “Why do we have to ship our food, our cows in South America with MERCOSUR? It is unreal today to sign such a treaty... for the future of our children and our planet.”

This statement was echoed by participants #14 (SI) and #13 (PL), who called for the protection of local markets and support for domestic production, especially for young entrants who cannot afford to compete on a large scale or absorb market shocks. There was a unified, cross-national call to recognise and support “quality European food” based on sustainability, safety and cultural tradition.

“The CAP should support farmers and especially young farmers — not just to protect the environment, but to produce. If it's just about protecting the environment, then Greenpeace should pay.” (#8, BE)

IV.2 Pressures and stresses

The policy-related pressures and stresses faced by young European farmers reflect a deeply structural and systemic dissonance between the lived reality of farming life and the framework conditions that are supposed to support it. In all five focus groups, participants articulated a deep sense of disconnectedness, disillusionment and administrative exhaustion with current agricultural policy – particularly the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

A key concern is the administrative burden and policy fragmentation that characterises the way subsidies and regulations are handled. Young farmers reported that they have to find their way through a labyrinth of changing rules, unclear requirements and inefficient supervisory systems. This bureaucratic pressure not only hinders efficiency, but also

contributes to chronic mental stress and demotivation, especially as the policy does not do justice to the diversity of regional conditions, farm sizes and stages of development.

Closely linked to this is the problem of economic uncertainty and barriers to entry, particularly for those who do not have family farms. Limited access to land, credit and capital means that many young aspirants are “out of the race” before they have even started. While the policy landscape offers formal subsidies, it is perceived as structurally inaccessible or poorly targeted, especially for new entrants or non-traditional succession models. This further entrenches generational inequality and hinders renewal.

The stress associated with generational renewal and succession planning was characterised not only by financial hurdles, but also by the emotional and cultural complexity of transitions. Participants urged policy tools – such as early investment support, mentoring programmes and retirement incentives – to facilitate a smoother handover, including outside the family line. These instruments were seen as essential to preserve both the knowledge and the management of the land.

Participants also argued for social protection as a policy priority, including maternity leave, pensions and mental health services. The lack of these basic entitlements was directly linked to burnout and alienation. Austria was cited as a rare positive example where maternity policies have tangibly improved well-being and gender equity in agriculture.

In addition, the young farmers emphasised the need for contextualised, modern rural education, particularly in relation to digital and management skills. Without equal access to training, rural youth face a growing knowledge gap that discourages them from engaging in agriculture. Gaps in infrastructure – such as language teachers or digital tools – further isolate rural communities.

Environmental policy also proved to be contested terrain. While farmers generally reaffirmed their commitment to sustainability, they criticised policies that impose uncompensated environmental burdens on already vulnerable small farms. The unequal distribution of environmental costs, particularly for those farming in protected areas, was perceived as unfair and counterproductive.

A lack of agricultural knowledge among the public exacerbates the stress of being misunderstood or maligned. Many participants reported harmful stereotypes, such as the notion that farmers merely “collect subsidies”. This misperception contributes to a growing gap between producers and consumers and fosters moral pressures that affect identity and pride in the profession.

Finally, participants from peripheral and mountain regions drew attention to territorial inequalities and emphasised that EU-wide policies are unable to adequately address regional differences in access to markets, services and support. The “one-size-fits-all” approach was perceived as ineffective and marginalising, as it pushes young people in underserved rural areas away from agriculture.

To summarise, young farmers do not experience policy as a neutral framework, but as a dense and often alienating system that reinforces the very pressures it is intended to alleviate. Their statements reflect a call for fairness, flexibility and dignity – not just in economic terms, but also in terms of recognition, care and political imagination that does justice to the complexity of rural life.

IV.3 Hopes

Amid widespread criticism of the existing agricultural policy framework, young European farmers articulate a pragmatic and forward-looking vision for reform – a vision that goes beyond dependence on subsidies and bureaucratic inefficiency to promote dignity, resilience and structural fairness. Their hopes reflect a deep-rooted desire for policies that align with rural realities while enabling a just transition for the next generation of farmers.

A central aspiration is the reform of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) into a more transparent, targeted and accessible system. Participants called for funding mechanisms that take account of farm size, regional context and environmental commitment – particularly to support small, young and environmentally committed producers. They are not simply calling for more aid, but for fairness, clarity and proportionality so that support reaches those most in need and not just the established few.

It is crucial that young farmers strive for a dignified path into and out of farming. They argue in favour of a comprehensive succession policy that includes start-up support for new entrants, pension incentives for older generations and support for non-family transfers – promoting continuity between generations without making inheritance a prerequisite. These measures aim to democratise access to agriculture and make it a viable option for those who do not have family land or capital.

Another important hope is the institutionalisation of social protection in agricultural policy. Participants emphasised the need for maternity leave, pensions, mental health care and flexible working arrangements – rights that already exist in other professions but are largely absent in agriculture. The vision is clear: agriculture must no longer be structurally excluded from the welfare state.

Education was also named as a cornerstone of renewal. The young farmers called for accessible, flexible and practice-orientated learning that is adapted to rural realities, enabling continued innovation and preventing depopulation. Vocational training, scholarships and integration into the digital and knowledge economy were seen as essential, not only for the empowerment of individuals, but also for the long-term vitality of rural areas.

Linked to this is the desire for territorial justice and rural cohesion. Participants emphasised the importance of policies that address spatial inequalities – Including underinvestment in peripheral areas, limited infrastructure and the additional burden of farming in protected or remote areas. Support for these areas is not seen as charity, but as recognition of the public good that these farmers provide in terms of landscape conservation, biodiversity and environmental stewardship.

Finally, on a cultural and political level, young farmers are longing for greater recognition of the societal value of agriculture. They call on the public to look beyond romantic or limiting stereotypes and instead recognise farming as a modern, skilled and essential profession that is central to food security, environmental sustainability and cultural continuity.

Essentially, their political hopes centre on a new social contract for agriculture: one that supports farmers not only as food producers, but also as stewards of land, culture and community, deserving of dignity, autonomy and collective respect.

IV.4 Conclusion

Young European farmers envision a **reimagined agricultural policy** that bridges the deep gap between the current framework conditions and rural reality. Their key demands include **fair access to land, capital and succession support** that enables a dignified entry into farming regardless of inheritance. They call for a **simplified, transparent CAP** that provides targeted support for small, young and environmentally conscious producers and overcomes bureaucratic overload and dependence on subsidies.

Equally urgent is the **integration of social protection** measures – such as maternity leave, pensions and mental health care – into agricultural policy to ensure that farmers are placed on an equal footing with other occupational groups. They also emphasise the importance of **education adapted to rural areas, digital infrastructure and territorial justice**, especially for remote and environmentally sensitive regions.

Finally, the young farmers seek **public recognition of agriculture's societal value**. They are pushing for a change in perception that sees agriculture not as an outdated labour, but as a **modern, vital profession** that is central to food security, environmental protection and cultural continuity. Their hopes reflect a call for a **new social contract** based on fairness, dignity and long-term sustainability.

APPENDIX 6: REFLEXIVITY STATEMENT

We observed both weaknesses and strengths in conducting online focus groups. Among the weaknesses, we identified that we covered too many (four) broad, albeit related, general topics, with approximately four questions for each, all planned for a 90-minute group discussion. From this perspective, it was preferable to have more (five) focus groups with fewer participants (5, 2, 2, 3, 5), as this allowed everyone to express their views and opinions. However, the main disadvantage was the lack of confrontations among participants. This may also have been due to the language barrier, as the discussion was in English and some participants were more proficient than others. As a result, most participants tended to agree or simply added another aspect. They often began by saying, "I agree with everything that has been said so far." This explains the lack of disagreement, objections, or even confrontations of differing opinions; however, there was a great diversity of expressed alternatives (hopes).

An observed advantage was that research participants commented on the scenario and introduced new topics in response to open questions. If a specific topic, such as mental health, was addressed within the framework of other topics, we did not address it explicitly, particularly since there were only 90 minutes available for all four extensive topics with 16 planned open questions.

Finally, conducting online focus group discussions proved advantageous in terms of inclusivity, as young people seem to be more comfortable online.

APPENDIX 7: KEY FINDINGS BY THEME

Table 9: Main Findings of Theme I – Discussing Main Drivers in Agriculture

Thematic Area	Description
Economic uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fluctuating market prices, high input costs, unfair value distribution. - Trade liberalisation & competition from lower-standard imports (e.g. MERCOSUR). - High land prices & debt hinder entry and investment. - Political instability increases uncertainty.
Generational Change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young farmers hesitant to take over due to infrastructure risks, unstable policies, and climate uncertainty. - Commitment exists but is challenged by modernization and fluctuating income.
Labour Shortages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficulty attracting/retaining workers due to low wages, poor working conditions, undervaluation. - Ageing workforce & lack of renewal force farms to consolidate or close.
Climate Change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Immediate impacts on crop cycles, pests, environmental compliance. - Policy contradictions frustrate farmers (e.g. conflicting rules on grazing vs. grassland maintenance).
Technological Advances	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimism for AI, automation, and precision farming. - Concern over digital divide and digital literacy gaps. - Risk of deepening inequalities without equitable infrastructure and training.
Gender & Inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Women lead in diversification, social farming, education, and sustainability. - Challenge traditional leadership roles in agriculture.
Political & Bureaucratic Instability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy inconsistency and bureaucratic burdens undermine long-term planning. - Disillusionment with EU/national policy processes.
Mental Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Issues raised about overwork, isolation, and stress from economic/environmental pressures and regulations.
Resilience & Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emphasis on diversification, niche production, and community-based models. - Desire for autonomy and stable local markets. - Technology seen as empowering when used democratically.
Overall Perspective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Balanced view: Structural vulnerabilities acknowledged, but emphasis on adaptation and agency. - Climate, tech, and politics are areas for proactive change rather than passive endurance.

Table 10: Main Findings of Theme II – Generational Renewal

Thematic Area	Description
Between tradition and innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Young farmers respect inherited values but want the freedom to modernise technologically, ecologically, and organisationally. - Friction arises when older generations resist change, limiting younger farmers' decision-making.
Structural inequalities and access restrictions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to land, capital, and policy benefits remains unequal, favouring established male-led family farms. - Barriers include land price inflation, credit tied to parental guarantees, CAP design flaws, and gender-biased training. - Women face institutional blind spots, including inadequate maternity arrangements.
Emotional labour for succession	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Succession involves psychological readiness, identity shifts, and relationship negotiations. - Stress, exhaustion, and isolation are common, but mental health issues remain stigmatized and under-treated.
Societal perceptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Farming is often portrayed as outdated or in crisis. - Young farmers are reshaping its image through education, community engagement, and modern approaches.
Uncertain future	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Climate change, volatile markets, and political instability influence succession decisions. - Larger farms can plan strategically, but smallholders are more exposed to systemic shocks.
Learning and knowledge flow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Call for more practical, land-based training to complement theoretical education. - Informal learning is not equally accessible to all, especially new entrants. - Gender and rural-urban disparities limit inclusivity in agricultural education.
Envisioned future farm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aimed at economic viability, technological modernity, and environmental and social sustainability. - Emphasis on flexibility, adaptability, well-being, and personal meaning. - Visions vary depending on geographic and contextual constraints.
Pressures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic insecurity, structural marginalisation, and entrenched hierarchies. - High emotional demands and cultural misrecognition. - Successors often inherit both assets and accumulated problems.
Hopes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Viable and modern inheritances, respectful succession models, and autonomy to shape the farm.

YOUTH PERSPECTIVES OF THE FUTURE ATTRACTIVENESS OF FARMING

- Breaking gender barriers and gaining cultural recognition for farming.
- Sustainable, people-centred farms that are economically resilient and environmentally responsible.

Table 11; Main Findings of Theme III – Working Conditions

Thematic Area	Description
Work-life balance and mental health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Boundaries between work and personal life are blurred. - Lack of structured leave, maternity provision, and replacement labour increases strain. - Mental health issues (stress, loneliness, anxiety) are common and normalised. - Cultural reluctance to address psychological health fosters a silent crisis.
Gender, family dynamics and invisible labour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Women's contributions remain under-recognised, with maternity leave incompatible with farming routines. - Family labour provides resilience but also creates tension and unpaid work expectations. - Lack of professional boundaries contributes to fragility in farm households.
Technological modernisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Automation and digital tools can reduce physical strain and labour shortages. - Barriers to adoption include high investment costs, lack of training, rural infrastructure deficits, and scepticism. - Benefits depend on skill development and peer knowledge sharing.
Labour shortages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ageing agricultural workforce, difficulty finding seasonal workers, and low attractiveness for youth. - Family labour fills gaps but is unsustainable and worsens succession challenges.
Social perception and moral pressure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public hostility, especially towards livestock sectors, can stigmatise farming families. - Bureaucratic oversight perceived as intrusive and mistrustful.
Economic vulnerability and structural uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low market prices, reliance on CAP subsidies, and delayed investment undermine security. - Political volatility reduces farmers' ability to plan and absorb shocks.
Pressures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intersecting economic, physical, emotional, and cultural forces reinforce overwork. - Gender inequalities, invisible care work, rapid technological demands, public misrecognition, and bureaucratic burdens are major stressors.
Hopes and opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology as a tool for time, flexibility, and intellectual freedom rather than production maximisation. - Fairer markets, reliable CAP support, and hiring of paid labour. - Desire for work-life balance, co-operative labour schemes, childcare, and peer learning networks. - Resilience envisioned as mutual care and solidarity.

YOUTH PERSPECTIVES OF THE FUTURE ATTRACTIVENESS OF FARMING

	- A new social contract linking dignity, autonomy, mental health, and community to economic viability.
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Table 12: Main Findings of Theme IV – Policy Needs:

Thematic Area	Description
Structural and financial barriers to entering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to land, start-up capital, and viable succession plans remain unequal. - New entrants outside family farming face prohibitive costs and limited credit. - Positive examples include start-up grants and succession schemes in France, Austria, and Estonia. - Calls for targeted support prioritising new entrants, small producers, and eco-committed farms, plus pension incentives for older farmers and mechanisms for non-family transfers.
Economic stability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Market fairness, predictable prices, and protection of local production are seen as more important than subsidies. - Opposition to cheap imports under trade deals like MERCOSUR. - Subsidies viewed as necessary but insufficient without functioning markets.
CAP reform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Current CAP seen as overly bureaucratic, opaque, and burdensome. - Application processes are complex, inconsistent, and fragmented. - Demand for simplification, transparency, and a Europe-wide framework supporting renewal, investment, and labour sustainability.
Social protection and work-life balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Priorities include maternity leave, healthcare, pensions, mental health support, and replacement labour services. - Austria's maternity and pension parity cited as exemplary. - Recognition of unpaid family work in pension entitlements seen as fairness.
Environmental measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Farmers value environmental stewardship but criticise costly eco-regulations lacking fair compensation. - Support for policies that remunerate ecological services and integrate environmental protection with economic viability.
Territorial cohesion and rural infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Peripheral and mountainous regions face distance to markets, lack of rural services, poor education and digital infrastructure, and higher costs. - Call for regionally differentiated CAP policies to address inequalities.
Cultural recognition and public perception	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need for public education and campaigns to improve 'food literacy' and restore respect for farming. - Call to defend EU food quality standards in trade deals and promote farming's social and cultural value.
Pressures from current policy framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bureaucratic overload, market instability, limited resource access, social protection gaps, and one-size-fits-all regulations.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Consequences include administrative fatigue, intergenerational inequality, and mistrust of institutions.
Hopes for redesigned policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Fair market architecture with targeted CAP reform.- Embedded social protection and investment in rural education, infrastructure, and digital capabilities.- Recognition of farmers as producers, stewards of land, culture, and community.- Policies to ensure dignity, autonomy, and sustainability.

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